

E2C2

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

Title	D4.2 Initial Dynamic Federated Graph-Based Modeler and Resource Monitoring
Document Owners	UPV
Contributors	ICCS, CERTH
Dissemination	Public (PU)
Date	30/06/2025
Version	1.0

Version History

Nr.	Date	Author (Organization)	Description
0.1	10/03/2025	Matilde Julián (UPV), Efstathios Karanastasis (ICCS)	Initial deliverable structure
0.2	30/04/2025	Matilde Julián (UPV)	Introduction and technical objectives.
0.3	02/05/2025	Ioanna Kapetanidou (CERTH), Juan Gascón (UPV)	Input to section 6.4. Initial inputs to sections 4 and 5
0.4	14/05/2025	Efstathios Karanastasis. Efthymios Chondrogiannis (ICCS)	Input to sections 3.2, 5.2, 7, 11 (Annex)
0.5	16/05/2025	Matilde Julián, Juan Gascón (UPV)	Executive summary and conclusions. Updates to section 6.
0.6	21/05/2025	Efstathios Karanastasis, Evangelos Psomakelis (ICCS)	Updates to sections 3.2, 5.2, 7, 11 (Annex)
0.7	04/06/2025	Matilde Julián, Juan Gascón (UPV), Efstathios Karanastasis, Evangelos Psomakelis (ICCS)	Final contributions
0.8	05/06/2025	Matilde Julián (UPV)	Prepared for quality review
0.9	27/06/2025	Gonçalo Rodrigues (UNP), Jan Harej (ARC), Alexandros Nizamis (CERTH)	Internal review
1.0	30/06/2025	Matilde Julián, Juan Gascón (UPV), Efstathios Karanastasis (ICCS)	Updates and final improvements

Disclaimer

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Acknowledgement

The ENACT project is funded by the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission under **Grant Agreement 101135423**.

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
APM	Application Programming Model
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCC	Cognitive Computing Continuum
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DoA	Description of Action
DGM	Dynamic Graph Modeller
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DRL	Deep Reinforced Learning
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GA	Grant Agreement
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
OS	Operating System
QoS	Quality of Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SOTA	State of the Art
SRM	Security Risk Modeller
SSD	Solid State Drive
TDCME	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VTE	Virtual Environment for Training
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language
ZTP	Zero-Touch Provisioning

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the outcomes of T4.2 “Dynamic Federated Graph-Based Modeler of Resources, Devices and Services”. The first of those outcomes is a real-time modelling and visualization tool named the Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM), which is part of the Modelling Layer of the ENACT architecture and is a core component of the platform. The DGM constructs a dynamic graph representation of the continuum based on the metrics obtained from the Orchestration Layer, which captures the key relationships between the different elements in the system, as well as their operational state. This graph is then retrieved and analysed by other components of the ENACT platform to optimise the continuum by performing different types of analysis, such as security risk assessment, performance forecasting or resource allocation. The component also provides a comprehensive user interface to visualize the graph, highlighting the most relevant information for the user.

The other outcome of T4.2 are the CCC Data Models, which provide a common representation of the system information, including the description of the devices and resources (including their main features and capabilities) and the main characteristics of the applications and services that will be deployed in the continuum, and telemetry data. To represent the aforementioned data, the CCC Data Models contain three main models, namely, the Application/Service Model, the Resource/Device Model and the Telemetry Model. The use of the CCC models enables automatic processing of the data by the rest of the components of the ENACT platform.

This document analyses the requirements identified for the DGM and CCC Data Models, including how they are fulfilled by the components, and describes the design and implementation of both components, as well as their implementation status at M18 of the project and their integration with other components of the ENACT platform. In addition, this deliverable discusses the methodology followed for the definition of these models and provides a detailed description of each model. During the next period, these components will be integrated in the pilots in order to fine-tune them according to the needs of real-life scenarios and perform the validation tasks.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

D4.2 “Initial Dynamic Federated Graph-Based Modeler and Resource Monitoring” presents the design and implementation of two of the components of the ENACT platform, namely, the Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) and the CCC Data Models.

The scope of this deliverable includes the design of the DGM and data model, their relationships with other components of the ENACT architecture, their implementation status at M18 of the ENACT project and some examples of their use in different scenarios, including their integration with other components of the ENACT platform.

2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This deliverable is produced within WP4 “Cloud-Edge Abstraction, Distributed Storage, Interoperability and Modelling” and presents the output of T4.2 “Dynamic Federated Graph-Based

Modeler of Resources, Devices and Services". The components of the ENACT architecture described in this deliverable have been designed and implemented following the requirements and specifications defined in T2.1 and T2.2. Next, they have been integrated with other ENACT components based on the interactions defined in the Reference Architecture (defined in T2.3). During the next period, those components will be tested and validated in the pilots (WP3). In parallel, they will be customised and improved based on the feedback received from the pilots (WP7).

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Section 1 (Executive Summary):** Provides a summary of most parts of the project in relation to this deliverable.
- **Section 2 (Introduction):** describes the purpose and scope and structure of this document, as well as its relation to other WP's and Tasks.
- **Section 3 (Requirements Analysis):** briefly presents the requirements for each component and describes how the components fulfil them.
- **Section 4 (Technical Objectives):** presents the technical objectives fulfilled by each of the components presented in this deliverable.
- **Section 5 (Position in the ENACT Architecture):** provides a general description of the relationships of each of the components presented in this document with the rest of the blocks of the ENACT architecture.
- **Section 6 (Dynamic Graph Modeller):** describes in detail the design and implementation of the Dynamic Graph Modeller. The description includes an overview of the component, its technological description, development status at M18 and some examples of use in the context of the ENACT project.
- **Section 7 (CCC Data Models):** describes in detail the CCC Data Models, including their status at M18 of the project and their use by the components of the ENACT platform.
- **Section 8 (Release Summary):** provides information of the M18 release of each component described in this deliverable.
- **Section 9 (Conclusions):** Provides concluding remarks and closes the deliverable.

In addition, the document includes an annex with the detailed description of the CCC Data Models.

3. Requirements Analysis

3.1 Requirement analysis regarding Dynamic Graph Modelling

This section briefly describes how the DGM addresses the requirements identified for this component. A complete description of these requirements can be found in D2.2 and D2.5.

C04.1 DGM data modelling.

The dynamic graph modeller represents functional and non-function properties of edge-cloud resources.

User access to a comprehensive, up-to-date representation of the different entities in the continuum, facilitating informed decision-making and effective system design and optimisation.

C04.2 DGM real-time visibility and dynamic updates.

The dynamic graph modeller should provide near real-time visibility and dynamic updates in the properties of distributed resources.

The dynamic graph modeller should provide near real-time visibility and dynamic updates in the properties of distributed resources.

C04.3 DGM visualisation features.

The Dynamic Graph Modeller should offer user-friendly visualisation features, including network topology visualisation, with support for zooming, panning, and filtering.

The Dynamic Graph Modeller offers intuitive visualisation features that help users to better understand specific parts of the network, identify patterns, and make informed decisions.

C04.4 DGM drag-and-drop functionality.

The dynamic graph modeller permits users to create and modify the visualization of graphs using drag-and-drop features.

The visualization of the graph should be interactive in the mean that users could interact with the graph visualization and reorganize it in the ways they want.

C0.4.5 DGM represents ENACT use-case scenarios.

The Dynamic Graph Modeller must represent the ENACT use-case scenarios topologies considering deployment heterogeneity and scalability.

The Dynamic Graph Modeller has to represent the ENACT continuum as a graph by this new form of visualization the DGM tries to improve the visualization for user. The main goal is to have a new visualization that will be used for the rest of users and in which in a glance can determine if their application is working properly and the distribution of the application among the resources available.

C0.4.6 Visualization of the SRM report in the DGM UI.

The dynamic graph modeller must show the results of Risk Assessment component.

As the Dynamic Graph Modeller has a frontend and UI to represent the graph visualization of the ENACT continuum another tab will be present on the UI to represent the risks report generated by the Security Risk Modeller component.

C0.4.7 DGM provides graph data to AI layer.

The dynamic graph modeller must provide graph data input to the AI layer.

The Dynamic Graph Modeller will generate a graph of the ENACT continuum and will be available at its API for the rest of the ENACT components that needs this data. In regard to the AI layer all their components will have access to the DGM API and in the case they need specifical graph for their purposes it will be created an endpoint for the customize graph data for the AI layer.

3.2 Requirement analysis regarding CCC Data Modelling

In this section, each of the platform requirements related to the CCC Data Models is briefly elaborated. Then, a short explanation is provided regarding how the CCC Data Models cover each requirement.

C05.1 - CCC Data models for standardised information collection and exchange

Data models need to be developed for describing applications / services, resources / devices and telemetry data in a standardised manner, using predefined structure and terminologies. The properties / parameters of the models should be defined.

This is the main requirement expressing the need for developing the CCC Data Models. To address this requirement, three structured CCC Data models were developed and the parameters for each class/entity were defined in close collaboration with ENACT component owners. Additionally, the models were extended with more classes and parameters based on the State of the Art, bibliography and the documentation of relevant components like Kubernetes¹ and Elastic².

C05.2 - Application / service data model

The description of each application / service should be accompanied with additional (deployment related) information that clearly specifies the particular application requirements and user expectations that should be fulfilled.

This requirement states the need for a model that allows the expression of the characteristics of an application or service to be deployed in the continuum. Also, the definition of particular deployment objectives by means of an elaborated set of available parameters. The developed Application model is a rich model that covers the aforementioned aspects with an extensive list of attributes modelled in several categories, such as usage demand, service level, performance, data storage and transfer, network, security and privacy, energy consumption, and cost, etc. These can cover the definition of application or service characteristics and the specification of deployment requirements from different perspectives. When instantiated from a user's perspective, it can offer a higher-level abstraction, whereas an expert user or software component can utilise the model for the specification of more low-level parameter values.

C05.3 - Resource / device data model

The resources and devices connected to the ENACT platform along with their particular characteristics and capabilities should be accurately described in a machine processable format.

This requirement expresses the need of having a model for enabling the detailed description of the CCC resources and devices along with their characteristics and capabilities. In order to tackle this requirement, the Resource model was developed. The model fully addresses the requirement, since it enables the expression of the various resource entities of the CCC (including standalone resources and attached resources, as well as physical resources and services) along with their characteristics, capabilities and configurations. It further models the connections among these entities and provides the relevant abstractions, wherever this is required.

C05.4 - Telemetry model

The detailed telemetry data stemming from the execution of applications in the available connected resources should be accurately described in a standardised, machine processable manner, so that they can be used by the rest of components of the ENACT platform.

This requirement expresses the need of having a model to describe in detail the various telemetry data and enable their sharing with the platform components. These data play a crucial role for

¹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/instrumentation/>

² <https://www.elastic.co/docs/reference/observability/>

monitoring the infrastructure as well as enabling the cognitive aspects of the compute continuum. The developed Telemetry model organises the telemetry data in various domains and enables their detailed expression for fulfilling the purposes of the ENACT platform.

C05.1.1 - Dynamic Graph Modeller data modelling**C05.1.2 - Telemetry Data Collection & Monitoring Engine data modelling****C05.1.3 - Orchestrator data modelling****C05.1.4 - AI Forecaster data modelling****C05.1.5 - Application Controller data modelling****C05.1.6 - Application Programming Model data modelling****C05.1.7 - AI Act Compliance Checker data modelling****C05.1.8 - Application Policy Model data modelling****C05.1.9 - Data Manager data modelling****C05.1.10 - Security Risk Modeller data modelling****C05.1.11 - AI-based Anomaly Detection data modelling**

The data modelling requirements of these components should be closely investigated in collaboration with the component developers.

The development of the CCC Data Models was primarily driven by the need to comprehensively address the data requirements of the relevant ENACT components. Initially, the list of components that would either utilise the CCC Data Models or influence their development was thoroughly discussed at the platform architecture design activities. Subsequently, a specific requirement was defined for each component, to examine and analyse its particular data needs, identify the relevant data parameters, and clarify their semantics prior to modelling. The implementation of these requirements is directly reflected in the three Data Models produced, particularly in the level of expressiveness achieved, which is sufficient to capture the information necessary to fulfil the scope of each component.

C05.3.1 - Represent resource configuration and static properties

The static characteristics that are defined at design/deployment time and not expected to change, and configurable parameters that can be adjusted by users or orchestrators of resources should be modelled, since they both portray important usable information.

This requirement is more closely related with the Resource model. The developed Resource model tackles this requirement by incorporating both aspects in clearly distinguished classes. It addresses both the static properties of resources (such as hardware capabilities, architectural features, and fixed identifiers) and their configurable parameters, which define aspects that can be (re-)adjusted or provisioned later on. This dual representation allows the model to capture the essential characteristics of a resource while also supporting dynamic configuration in orchestrated environments. When used in conjunction with the Telemetry model, which captures runtime metrics and observations, the two models together realise a triadic modelling approach: specification, configuration, and telemetry. This separation of concerns enables clarity, modularity, and adaptability in various CCC systems.

C05.1.12 - Enable semantic distinction between concepts and observations

The models should capture the separation of semantic intent of entities and parameters from their realised form to the extent possible while maintaining model complexity at acceptable levels.

In complex system models, it is indeed essential to distinguish between the conceptual definitions that describe what a system is concerned with, and the actual observations or measurements that represent how those concerns manifest in practice. This approach separates the semantic intent of a parameter or class (such as a resource type, capability, or measurable quantity) from its realised form, which may vary depending on context, measurement, or instantiation.

The CCC Data Models have been developed following this concept. For example, a telemetry parameter may define the metric of "CPU utilisation" in an abstract manner, while a *Measurement Value* captures a specific observation (e.g., 72%, measured at a given time, in a given unit, via a specific methodology). Similarly, a *Resource*, can include both *Standalone* and *Attached Resource* classes, which in turn define the semantic role of the respective entities. When instantiated, these classes can define the capabilities of particular system components. These distinctions improve the clarity, modularity, and interoperability of the developed models, and allow for flexibility and adaptability, including mapping between abstract system knowledge and operational data, as well translating and consolidating information coming from different connected systems.

4. Technical Objectives

This deliverable describes the design and implementation of the DGM and CCC Data Models. On the one hand, the DGM aims to deliver a modelling studio environment able to provide a comprehensive graph representation of the ENACT CCC, thus enabling efficient and scalable analysis, control and optimization of the system by applying machine learning techniques on the graph data. On the other hand, the CCC Data Models allow for the modelling of complex systems comprising heterogeneous and dynamic resources, devices and services.

These components fulfil Operational Objective #1 (OO#1) of the project: "Provide mechanisms to optimise the execution of distributed applications (across Edge to Cloud) and proactively balance and optimise the compute swarm according to needs and opportunities in the CCC". The DGM offers a real-time visual modelling environment that allows the infrastructure engineers and administrators to generate and visualize graph models of the resources in the CCC in real-time. The integration of the DGM with other components of the ENACT architecture enables dynamic capture and processing of information from the CCC, following the common CCC Data Models to ensure interoperability. Moreover, the DGM will be able to provide reliable information (based on the ingestion of telemetry data from Edge and Cloud resources) about the status of connectivity or edges between different nodes, the utilisation of nodes by different applications and other non-functional characteristics that are needed for enabling efficient management of distributed infrastructure in federated CCC (such as resource availability, communication frequency, power consumption, energy mix, etc). Moreover, the DGM and CCC Models, together with this deliverable, contribute to ENACT's milestone MS4 "Initial ENACT core components availability".

Finally, these components contribute to the fulfilment of the following WP4 objectives:

- Perform the necessary developments, setups and integrations at (and between) the Cloud and Edge levels in order to enable the realisation of the integrated compute continuum that allows dynamic deployments, data management and load-balancing.

- Provide the integration and interoperability mechanisms including relevant protocols and policies that ensure trustworthy and secure communication at different levels in the compute continuum.

5. Position in the ENACT Architecture

5.1 Dynamic Graph Modeller

The Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) collects real-time metrics and application data from the Orchestration layer of the ENACT continuum and constructs a dynamic graph used by the Modelling and AI layers. It serves as the bridging component that interconnects these three layers, enabling the flow of contextual and system-level information.

This graph facilitates a new point of view of the ENACT continuum for visualization, risk assessment, and predictive analytics to support intelligent decision-making. Figure 1 below illustrates the DGM's role in the ENACT architecture, showing how it interfaces with each layer and the specific components it connects.

Figure 1: Diagram of the DGM in the ENACT architecture

5.2 CCC Data Models

Given its role and position in the ENACT architecture, as described above, the Dynamic Graph Modeller processes a significant volume of real-time information to visualise the Compute Continuum and relay it to other ENACT components. This data is transferred in the background using the CCC Data Models. As outlined in deliverable D2.4, the CCC Data Models are not a component of the ENACT platform per se, but rather a collection of semantic and data models that define the data structures and attributes available for use by ENACT platform components, either internally or for information exchange. Apart from the DGM, several other ENACT components make use of the CCC Data Models, which include three main models. The Application Model describes application characteristics and deployment requirements and goals to optimise performance and resource allocation in the ENACT Continuum. The Resource Model represents detailed characteristics of

hardware and software resources in the ENACT Continuum, supporting extensibility and diverse computing capabilities. The Telemetry Model captures real-time infrastructure metrics to monitor resource states and support dynamic decision-making in the ENACT Continuum.

Figure 2, below, stemming from deliverable D2.6, depicts the ENACT platform components that make use of the CCC Data Models parameters. As the legend on the figure also indicates, the components that utilise the CCC Data Models internally and/or for external communications are shown with bold font and a thick outline. The list of components spans across all layers of the ENACT platform architecture, and includes the Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) and the Security Risk Modeller (SRM) in the Modelling Layer, the Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME) and the Orchestrator in the Orchestration Layer, the AI Forecaster in the AI Layer, the Application Controller, Application Programming Model (APM), AI Act Compliance Check and Application Policy Model in the Application Development Layer, and the Data Manager in the Data Layer.

Figure 2: CCC Data Models in the ENACT architecture

6. Dynamic Graph Modeller

6.1 Overview

The Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) is a core component of the ENACT architecture designed to provide a real-time representation of the system's operational state across the Orchestration,

Modelling, and AI layers. It builds and updates a dynamic graph that captures key relationships between components, services, and metrics, enabling intelligent reasoning and decision support.

By continuously ingesting telemetry data, application metrics, and contextual information from the Orchestration layer, the DGM constructs a graph-based model that is consumed by other ENACT's components such as the Security Risk Modeller and the AI Forecaster. This model serves as the foundation for advanced analysis, such as security risk assessment, resource allocation, energy harvesting, and so on.

Through its user-facing interface, the DGM also allows human operators to visualize the graph, enhancing situational awareness of both, the physical infrastructure and the software components (applications) deployed on it.

The DGM acts as a bridge between the operational and cognitive aspects of the ENACT continuum, ensuring that all layers operate with a consistent and updated view of the deployment environment.

6.2 Technological description

The DGM consists of two main components, the backend and the frontend (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Subcomponents of the DGM

6.2.1 Backend

The backend retrieves real-time telemetry data, metrics and contextual information from the Orchestration layer and constructs the graph of the actual state of the architecture (physical devices) and deployments (applications).

The backend is developed with the **Python**³ programming language using **FastAPI**⁴ as the framework to build the API-REST (Figure 4). The graph generation is done by the library **Networkx**⁵, that is a

³ <https://www.python.org/>

⁴ <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>

⁵ <https://networkx.org/>

powerful library for generation and treatment of graphs in Python. During graph generation (Figure 5) the Graph Data Requester module interacts with the Orchestration layer components to gather the metrics and context data of the continuum and with this info the graph is generated.

Figure 4: DGM backend implementation

Figure 5: DGM backend graph generation request flow diagram

Figure 6: DGM frontend implementation

6.2.2 Frontend

The frontend is developed using the **Typescript**⁶ programming language and using the **React**⁷ library for the UI and is a compound of two modules (Figure 6):

- **The Graph Visualization** module that represents the graph of the continuum, to represent the graph, the library **Sigmajs**⁸ is used. This is a **Javascript**⁹ library that enables the representation and visualization of graphs.
- **The SRM Report Visualization** module shows the report file generated by the SRM component once this component digests from the graph the status and data of the continuum (Figure 7).

⁶ <https://www.typescriptlang.org/>

⁷ <https://react.dev/>

⁸ <https://www.sigmajs.org/>

⁹ <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/JavaScript>

Figure 7: DGM frontend graph and SRM report visualization flow diagram

The current version of the UI consists of a navigation bar in which it can be selected the different views available and a container in which the graphs are rendered, and the users can interact with. The views available are:

- Cluster nodes (Figure 8)
- Pods (Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11)
- SRM report visualization (Figure 12)
- AI graph visualization (Figure 13)

Figure 8: Representation of cluster nodes running in the ENACT continuum

Figure 9: Representation of pods that are deploying and running on a cluster node.

Figure 10: Representation that highlights the connections of a selected pod

Figure 11: Representation of how an application is distributed among the different cluster nodes

DCM Node Visualization Pod Visualization **SRM Report** AI Visualization

Label	Asset	Assertable	Proposed	Work in Progress																																		
SLA	system#replicaset_open5gs-sgwu-6b5798bfd	Yes	No	No																																		
SoftwareTesting	system#container_open5gs-sgwu	Yes	No	No																																		
X509ServiceVerifier	system#pod_open5gs-scp-5cc5c9674f-9ghwk	Yes	No	No																																		
SoftwarePatched	system#pod_open5gs-mongodb-7d98bfc976-cvg4g	Yes	No	No																																		
SuspendInfectedProcess	system#LoginService_replicaset_open5gs-ausf-86f8588766	Yes	No	No																																		
X509ClientVerifier	system#replicaset_open5gs-pcrf-b4b665f5	Yes	No </tr <tr> <td>KeyManagement</td> <td>system#container_open5gs-nrf-DataService</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>No</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>PenetrationTesting</td> <td>system#pod_open5gs-mongodb-7d98bfc976-cvg4g</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>No</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>DisableServiceAccess</td> <td>system#Interface_container_open5gs-upf_InternetAsset</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>No</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>X509</td> <td>system#LoginService_container_open5gs-amf</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>No</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>AccessControl</td> <td>system#LoginService_container_open5gs-mme</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>No</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>RestrictedShell</td> <td>system#LoginService_replicaset_open5gs-udr-5f7bff976</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>No</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FormalVerification</td> <td>system#container_open5gs-scp-DataService</td> <td>Yes</td> <td>No</td> <td>No</td> </tr>	KeyManagement	system#container_open5gs-nrf-DataService	Yes	No	No	PenetrationTesting	system#pod_open5gs-mongodb-7d98bfc976-cvg4g	Yes	No	No	DisableServiceAccess	system#Interface_container_open5gs-upf_InternetAsset	Yes	No	No	X509	system#LoginService_container_open5gs-amf	Yes	No	No	AccessControl	system#LoginService_container_open5gs-mme	Yes	No	No	RestrictedShell	system#LoginService_replicaset_open5gs-udr-5f7bff976	Yes	No	No	FormalVerification	system#container_open5gs-scp-DataService	Yes	No	No
KeyManagement	system#container_open5gs-nrf-DataService	Yes	No	No																																		
PenetrationTesting	system#pod_open5gs-mongodb-7d98bfc976-cvg4g	Yes	No	No																																		
DisableServiceAccess	system#Interface_container_open5gs-upf_InternetAsset	Yes	No	No																																		
X509	system#LoginService_container_open5gs-amf	Yes	No	No																																		
AccessControl	system#LoginService_container_open5gs-mme	Yes	No	No																																		
RestrictedShell	system#LoginService_replicaset_open5gs-udr-5f7bff976	Yes	No	No																																		
FormalVerification	system#container_open5gs-scp-DataService	Yes	No	No																																		

Figure 12: SRM report visualization

DCM Node Visualization Pod Visualization SRM Report **AI Visualization**

Original Graph **AI Graph**

Figure 13: AI graph visualization in which it shows the input and the output graph after being processed by the AI layer

6.3 Development status (M18)

The development status could be followed at the Gitlab repository¹⁰ of the component. Specially at the "Issue boards" section¹¹ in which it could be followed the development and the current status of the component. As a summary, the status of the component is the following:

¹⁰ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/dynamic-graph-modeller>

¹¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/dynamic-graph-modeller/-/boards>

Backend

- **Overall architecture:** The system is built using a microservices architecture and ready to be deployed on a Kubernetes cluster.
- **Implemented APIs:** Core endpoints for data graph retrieval and basic customization of the requests to make available to only query defined resources are completed; include more customization of the requests besides the inclusion of new metrics and info to the graph still under development.
- **Database and storage:** Redis is used for caching and short-term data and it is fully integrated.
- **External integrations:** Successfully connected with Hubble (Cilium) and TDCME for graph generation and metrics. Integration with other layers (AI and Orchestration) are under development.

Frontend

- **Architecture:** Developed using React with a modular component structure.
- **Available views:** Graph visualization of the continuum with some filtering (like namespace for instance).
- **API consumption:** All available backend endpoints are consumed and integrated through Axios with retry logic and error handling.
- **Interaction and business logic:** Dynamic filters, node selection, and real-time graph updates are implemented. Form validations and feedback modals are functional.
- **Styling and design:** Fully responsive UI built with Tailwind CSS. Matches the defined design system.

Finally, the next steps regarding the DGM will be mainly focused on its integration and validation in the pilots. More concretely, the following actions will be performed:

- Support WP3 partners in the integration of the DGM in the different use cases.
- Issue reporting.
- Improvement of the component based on the feedback received from the pilots.
- Test and validation.

6.4 Use cases & integration

The **Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM)** serves as a core component that transforms the ENACT's continuum into a dynamic graph structure. This graph representation enables other components to observe and extract the actual state of the continuum and act in consequence if needed.

Integration

The DGM integrates with the overall architecture by:

- **Continuously ingesting data** about edge and cloud resources and transforming it into a coherent, structured graph.
- **Exposing this graph through APIs or data interfaces**, making it consumable by components in the AI and Orchestration layers.
- **Providing a frontend representation** of the graph for human inspection, debugging, and exploratory analysis.

Enabling Use Cases (via Integration)

By supplying a lively and structured view of the system, the DGM enables a variety of use cases in other components, such as:

- **AI-based optimization:** AI components can traverse the graph to identify optimal resource allocation strategies or predict future states.
- **Intent-based orchestration:** Orchestration modules use the graph to understand resource topology and constraints for better deployment decisions.
- **Policy compliance:** Policy engines query the graph to enforce location, performance, or regulatory constraints dynamically.
- **Security analysis:** Detection of anomalous connections, isolation violations, or unauthorized dependencies.
- **Root cause analysis:** When integrated with observability data, the graph helps trace faults or performance issues to their origin.

7. CCC Data Models

The CCC Data Models specifications were initially provided in deliverable D2.1 and updated in D2.4. The role of the models in the ENACT architecture and the platform components that make use of them were described in deliverable D2.3, updated in D2.6, and summarised in section 5.2 of this deliverable. Also, the requirements pertaining to the development of the CCC models, were first elaborated in deliverable D2.2 and finalised in D2.5. In this deliverable, D4.2, a summary of this information is provided, for reasons of completeness. Additionally, the methodology followed for the development of the CCC models is briefly discussed. Finally, the relation of the developed models to the expressed requirements is explained.

7.1 Overview

7.1.1 Purpose and main concepts

As already mentioned in section 5.2 above, the CCC Data Models encompass three different models: The Application model, the Resource model and the Telemetry model, which are presented in more detail in the following sections. Each of these models semantically represents a particular domain of interest and defines the relevant data structures that can be utilised by the ENACT platform components. The data are organised into multi-level classes and subclasses, starting with the more generic/abstract principles/categories and gradually focusing on more specific ones.

The development of the CCC Data Models served multiple purposes. First, they provide a specification for data interoperability within the ENACT platform, fully addressing the needs of its components. Second, they encapsulate the key data aspects of the Cognitive Compute Continuum domain, making them applicable to other relevant systems and use cases.

The models follow important modelling principles and good practices to ensure clarity, modularity, and semantic rigor, and are designed to be generalisable and easily extensible. Some of these principles and concepts were also expressed and dictated via the CCC-models-related requirements, as already outlined in section 3.2.

A core modelling strategy applied is the separation of concerns, distinguishing between resource capabilities, configurable settings, and runtime behaviour, reflected in the adoption of a triadic modelling pattern (specification, configuration, and telemetry) where each model addresses a specific system perspective: the Resource model defines what a resource is, its low-level capabilities and how it can be configured, and the Telemetry model represents dynamic runtime metrics. Additionally, the Application model is meant for capturing application characteristics and deployment requirements in high- or intermediate-level manner, depending on whether it is being used by a human being (expertise can vary) or a machine.

To promote consistency and extensibility, the models enforce a clear distinction between types and instances, and between parameters and their observed values. Abstract classes allow reuse across various components, while inheritance is used to reflect semantic specialisation. Relationships like aggregation and composition are modelled to capture ownership and containment where appropriate.

The models prioritise semantic clarity, ensuring that each attribute or class has a precise meaning and avoiding redundancy. This design approach supports extensibility, enabling future integration and adaptation across evolving computing environments and potential alignment with broader modelling standards.

7.1.2 Methodology

This section outlines the methodology followed for the development of the CCC Models. The first step was to conduct thorough review of the state of the art (SotA) to identify relevant research and existing initiatives that could serve as a foundation for developing the CCC Data Models. As outlined in Deliverable D2.1, the initial key reference identified was the ARDIA framework, developed under the EU-funded SERRANO project. The ARDIA models provided a valuable starting point for ENACT's data modelling efforts.

Later in the process, another significant and recent contribution was discovered, the aerOS continuum ontology, developed within the EU-funded aerOS project, as presented in the updated SotA section of Deliverable D2.4. This ontology helped refine the models further by introducing additional parameters and attributes for various entities. Both ARDIA and aerOS were thoroughly analysed with respect to their modelling approaches, core entities, and associated attributes.

In parallel, a collaborative spreadsheet was shared with all ENACT consortium partners involved in developing platform components, enabling them to specify the data parameters required for the operation of their solutions, components, or algorithms. The input was collected per component and then carefully analysed and categorised into the three data models according to the nature of the information. These requirements were then integrated with findings from existing initiatives identified in the SotA, and semantically processed to extract unique parameters, remove redundancies, and organise the data hierarchically.

The outcome of this process was an initial version of the CCC Data Models, which was presented to ENACT partners for feedback. Following the review, a second version was proposed, which initiated a series of one-on-one discussions and close collaboration with the individual component owners. These discussions helped clarify specific needs, required parameters, and their intended use. After these refinements, the final version of the data models was produced, which is presented in this deliverable.

7.2 Models description

This section provides the three developed CCC Data Models in terms of structure and parameters. The parameters are organised into classes that follow hierarchies and contain attributes. The structure and dependencies are provided by the means of a UML class diagram. To enhance understanding, the classes are then presented in tables. The complete list of classes and attributes along with suggested data types is provided in the Annex 10 of this deliverable.

7.2.1 Application model

The Application Model provides a structured framework for describing the characteristics and deployment objectives of applications in distributed, intelligent computing environments. The model is centred around a root class, `Application`, which aggregates high-level aspects of an application, organising them into a hierarchy of conceptual domains.

Each primary domain, such as Performance, Deployment, Data, or Security, is modelled as a subclass of `Application`, and includes specific parameters as attributes. These parameters cover both static characteristics of applications and dynamic properties including deployment goals and expectations.

The model also integrates an extended domain for Artificial Intelligence, capturing the specific requirements and configuration options for AI components embedded in CCC applications. This includes aspects like model deployment, AI resource scaling, and AI-specific performance metrics, structured under the `Artificial Intelligence` class and linked to the broader `Application` structure. The AI part of the model mainly focuses on the compliance checking perspective, as it has been created by carefully considering and analysing the templates intended for application providers to grant them the required information for AI compliance check of their applications. These templates are categorised by risk level to ensure accuracy and alignment with compliance standards. Additionally, the template designed and used for initial risk level categorisation was included and used, which helps determine the risk level of the provided system across all categories. The overall intention was to carefully model this information as exactly obtained via the templates, so that the Application model could be used for the provision of this information, thus alleviating in the future the need to provide it via separately distributed documents, as is currently done. There are thirteen sub-classes to the main Artificial Intelligence class.

The UML diagram of the Application model is presented in Figure 14. To simplify the diagram and improve readability, only the first two levels of the Artificial Intelligence domain are shown. The part of the model that corresponds to the AI domain, is provided separately in the diagram of Figure 15, which is split into two halves for better readability. The left half presents the upper part of the diagram, whereas the right half presents its lower part. Although every effort was made to provide high-quality images, it is understandable that they may not be easily legible when viewed directly within this document. Readers who wish to visually explore the model details are encouraged to use the links provided in section 8 to image visualisations that allow for unrestricted zooming and navigation.

Figure 14: UML diagram of Application model

Figure 15: UML diagram of Application model - Artificial Intelligence part

Table 1 provides an overview of Application model classes ordered alphabetically. It includes Artificial Intelligence domain classes up to level 2 of hierarchy.

Class Name	Description
AcceptableApproximation	Defines tolerable deviations in accuracy when operating under constrained resources.
Accuracy	Indicates the degree of correctness in the application's output. Crucial for applications involving calculations, AI inference, or critical decision-making.
AdversarialTestingModelAdaptation	Outlines techniques for testing the robustness of the AI system against adversarial inputs, and mechanisms for adapting the model post-deployment.
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	Describes the full lifecycle and methodology used in the development of the AI system, including cybersecurity, validation, human oversight, and system design practices.
Application	Top-level class that aggregates all metadata, requirements, and context about the software entity.
ArtificialIntelligence	Represents AI-specific characteristics of the application, including compliance, performance, and explainability, as required by the EU AI Act. Includes regulatory documentation, risk assessments, performance evaluation, and system architecture details.
AuthorisationAndAccessControl	Represents authentication and permission systems regulating user and system access.
Availability	Details the uptime and recovery requirements for the application. Useful for assessing operational resilience and fault tolerance.
Bandwidth	Represents the available or required data transmission rate in the network.
Cores	Indicates the number of processor cores available or required for executing application tasks.
Cost	Describes financial expenditure related to deploying and running the application in specific configurations.
CPU	Specifies the processor characteristics required for application execution, including architecture and vendor.
DataEncryption	Specifies encryption standards and methods used to secure data at rest or in transit.
DataObject	Represents structured or unstructured data entities processed or produced by the application.
DataRetrieval	Defines how and how quickly data is accessed from storage or remote sources.
DataStorage	Encapsulates characteristics of persistent storage used, including type, performance, and location.
DataTransfer	Covers the movement of data between nodes, including protocol, frequency, and integrity guarantees.
Deployment	Represents the configuration and environment in which the application is deployed, including how long it runs, what environment it's in, and how many replicas are provisioned.
DetailedDescriptionGeneral	Provides a structured summary of the AI system's purpose, context, design philosophy, and general functioning, as outlined in regulatory technical documentation.
Details	Stores metadata that uniquely identifies the application, such as its name, type, ID, and access endpoint. Useful for cataloguing and referencing the application in larger systems.
Development	Encapsulates metadata and tools used during the application development phase.
Duration	Aggregates timing information related to the application's lifecycle, including the full span of operation and any scheduled operational windows.
Energy	Specifies the energy consumption profile or constraints of application deployment and execution.
EnergyAndCost	Captures resource usage and associated costs, including power consumption and economic cost.

EraseCoding	Defines use of data redundancy techniques to improve storage reliability and fault tolerance.
EUDeclarationConformity	Represents the formal declaration that the AI system complies with EU regulations. Includes conformance with mandatory and harmonized standards.
EvaluationStrategies	Details the evaluation protocols, testing strategies, and performance criteria used to assess the AI system's effectiveness and reliability.
Execution	Describes runtime characteristics such as duration, frequency, and execution context of the application.
ExecutionEnvironment	Specifies the operating system, hardware, and runtime context where the application executes.
Freshness	Indicates the temporal relevance or age of data required by or generated by the application.
GeneralDescription	Summarizes the system-level perspective of the AI solution, including its components, purpose, and deployment context.
GeographicalLocation	Specifies the physical geographic region (e.g., country, data centre) where application services run.
HardwareAcceleration	Specifies the use of specialized hardware (e.g., GPU, TPU) to enhance application performance.
HarmonisedStandards	Lists the harmonized technical standards followed during development to demonstrate compliance with the EU AI Act.
InputData	Defines the type, structure, and requirements of data received by the application.
Latency	Measures the time delay between request and response during data transfer or execution.
LifecycleChanges	Captures modifications made to the AI system across its lifecycle, including updates, patches, or versioning processes.
Location	Captures the physical or logical deployment site of application components.
MonitoringFunctioningControl	Describes ongoing mechanisms for monitoring the behaviour and performance of the AI system after deployment, including anomaly detection and intervention points.
Network	Specifies the communication infrastructure connecting different application components.
NetworkCapacity	Specifies the throughput and load handling capacity of the network used by the application.
OtherTechnicalDetails	Captures miscellaneous or advanced configuration details not covered in standard categories.
OutputData	Describes the data generated or returned as a result of application execution.
Overall	Defines the total operational timeline of the application from its initial start to final shutdown. Important for historical tracking and audit purposes.
Performance	Captures execution performance metrics including responsiveness, latency, and throughput under defined conditions.
PerformanceMetrics	Details the metrics used for evaluation of the AI system's performance.
PostMarketMonitoring	Specifies the strategy and tools for monitoring the AI system's behaviour and compliance once it's in the market. Aligns with post-market obligations in the EU AI Act.
Privacy	Describes mechanisms and policies for protecting personal or sensitive information.
RAM	Represents the system's volatile memory characteristics needed for application operation.
RAMCapacity	Defines the required or available size of random-access memory in units such as GB or MB.
Range	Specifies a concrete time range with a start and end, often used within durations or scheduled activities. Useful for specifying exact periods for analysis or availability.
Reliability	Describes the application's ability to perform consistently over time, including failure rates. Important for long-term maintainability and service continuity.
RequestsNumber	Quantifies the application's request load, both concurrent and over time. Key for sizing infrastructure and monitoring performance.

RiskManagement	Represents the systematic identification, analysis, and mitigation of risks associated with the AI system, required for high-risk systems under the EU AI Act.
Scaling	Describes how the application should handle increased load through additional instances. Useful for autoscaling and elasticity strategies.
Scheduled	Specifies specific windows during which the application is scheduled to be available. Used for planned operation or maintenance scheduling.
Security	Captures technical and procedural mechanisms protecting the application from threats and vulnerabilities.
SecurityAndPrivacy	Encompasses requirements for data confidentiality, integrity, and authorized access.
ServiceLevel	Captures high-level service quality metrics, including accuracy, availability, and reliability. Often forms the basis for SLAs and user trust.
SoftwareDependencies	Lists external packages, modules, or services the application relies on.
SoftwareEnvironment	Describes the software stack required for execution, including OS, libraries, and services.
StorageDevice	Details the physical or virtual device used for storing application data (e.g., SSD, HDD).
SystemArchitecture	Describes the architectural design of the AI system, including hardware/software dependencies, data flows, and modular structure.
TimePeriod	Defines the temporal boundaries used to measure application metrics. Useful for defining the context for usage analytics or reporting intervals.
Timing	Captures timing constraints or benchmarks related to task execution or system responsiveness.
Token	Indicates use of identity tokens or digital certificates in secure access workflows.
Type	Classifies components (e.g., storage, processing) by their technology or purpose within the deployment environment.
UsageDemand	Describes patterns of application usage over time, including how often it's accessed, how it scales, and the number and type of users interacting with it.
UseFrequency	Describes how often the application is accessed or triggered by end-users or systems. This is critical for understanding workload patterns.
Users	Represents the user base interacting with the application, including metrics for user count and concurrency levels.
UsersNumber	Breaks down the user count into concurrent users and total users over a defined period. Helpful for performance tuning and scaling decisions.

Table 1: Overview of Application model classes

A table in Annex 10.1 provides a detailed view of all Application model classes and attributes, also including the full details of the Artificial Intelligence domain model.

7.2.2 Resource model

This model defines a detailed and extensible resource abstraction framework tailored for the CCC, capturing the heterogeneity, dynamism, and complexity of modern distributed computing environments. At its foundation lies a `Resource` superclass, which branches into `StandaloneResource` entities, representing independently functional resources such as compute nodes and storage systems, and `AttachedResource` components, such as GPUs, FPGAs, DPUs, and SmartNICs, which are hosted and managed by primary resources. The model distinctly separates capability specifications (e.g., hardware properties, supported features, operational constraints) from configuration aspects (e.g. provisioning details, enabled settings, resource limits), thus enabling a precise representation of both what a resource can achieve and how it is currently configured.

The Resource model incorporates extensive modelling for compute, storage, memory and networking domains, with each domain further detailed through its own set of specifications and configuration parameters, while energy and thermal aspects are modelled extensively. The model

supports advanced storage representations by incorporating data entities like `StorageObject` and `StorageFile`, allowing for fine-grained modelling of data items stored within a system. The incorporation of configuration interfaces for each resource type supports introspection, adaptation, and system-level orchestration.

Execution environments are represented through pods and containers, each possessing its own set of specifications and configurations, thereby facilitating deployment modelling at multiple levels of abstraction. Nodes aggregate and host multiple services and components, and they are further enriched with information such as architectural layout, physical placement, and deployment domain information.

Thermal profiles, energy efficiency ratings, virtualisation support, and hardware acceleration capabilities are also included, making the model well-suited for performance-aware and energy-efficient deployment planning.

Overall, the Resource model provides a semantically rich, modular, and comprehensive representation of resources across the CCC, supporting both high-level abstraction and low-level system details. In addition to the explicit capability and configuration dimensions, the model is designed with an inherent flexibility that enables it to be easily integrated with the CCC Telemetry model to provide a comprehensive triad approach encompassing specification, configuration, and telemetry. Binding the two models offers a holistic view of resource management, to support advanced orchestration, monitoring, and adaptive control in Cognitive Compute environments.

The UML diagram of the Resource model is presented in Figure 16.

Table 2 provides an overview of Resource model classes ordered alphabetically.

Class Name	Description
AttachedResource	Represents a resource component that is dependent on or mounted within a host system.
ConfigInterface	Represents the interface for accessing and managing configuration settings of a resource.
Container	Represents a single container instance within a pod, including runtime and configuration details.
ContainerConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a Container.
ContainerSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a Container.
CPU	Represents central processing units or their subcomponents, including sockets and specifications.
CPUConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a CPU.
CPUEnergy	Represents the energy aspect of a CPU.
CPUSocket	Represents Central Processing Units sockets.
CPUSocketConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a CPUSocket.
CPUSocketSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a CPUSocket.
CPUspec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a CPU.
DeploymentDomain	Describes deployment-domain-specific metadata, such as provider, region, or cost tier.
DPU	Represents a Data Processing Unit, detailing its capabilities and configuration.
DPUConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a DPU.
DPUEnergy	Represents the energy aspect of a Data Processing Unit.
DPUspec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a DPU.
Energy	Captures energy-related characteristics such as consumption, efficiency, and power constraints.
EnergyConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of Energy.
EnergySpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of Energy.
ExecutionInterface	Interface that specifies the methods and contracts required for executing workloads on a resource.
ExecutionService	Defines execution-related capabilities and runtime management for compute services.
ExecutionServiceConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a ExecutionService.
ExecutionServiceSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a ExecutionService.
FPGA	Represents a Field Programmable Gate Array and related characteristics.
FPGAConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a FPGA.
FPGAEnergy	Represents a Field Programmable Gate Array energy-related aspects.
FPGASpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a FPGA.
GPU	Represents a Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) and its associated attributes.
GPUConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a GPU.
GPUEnergy	Represents a Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) energy-related attributes.
GPUSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a GPU.
Location	Provides geographical and jurisdictional metadata for a storage or compute resource.
MemoryComponent	Abstract class that describes memory components or profiles, including capacity, performance, and usage context.
MemoryConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of Memory.
MemoryProfile	Describes memory components or profiles, including capacity, performance, and usage context.
MemorySpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of Memory.

Node	Represents a physical or virtual host that can manage and aggregate compute and storage services.
NodeConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a Node.
NodeSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a Node.
Pod	Encapsulates a group of containers that are deployed together on the same node.
PodConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a Pod.
PodSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a Pod.
Processor	Abstract base class for processing units such as CPUs, DPUs, and FPGAs, representing common computational characteristics.
Resource	Base class for all resource types in the CCC Resource model.
SharedMemory	Describes shared memory components or profiles, including capacity, performance, and usage context.
SmartNIC	Represents a Smart Network Interface Card with advanced offloading and virtualisation features.
SmartNICConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a SmartNIC.
SmartNICEnergy	Represents a Smart Network Interface Card energy-related attributes.
SmartNICSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a SmartNIC.
StandaloneResource	Represents an independent resource capable of operating on its own, such as a node or service.
Storage	Represents a physical or logical storage backend, including its location, vendor, and capacity.
StorageConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a Storage.
StorageFile	Models individual data files that might be handled, transferred, or managed by services or systems.
StorageFile	Represents a traditional file stored within a storage system.
StorageObject	Represents a storage entity in an object store.
StorageService	Defines storage-related capabilities and management for persistent or temporary storage.
StorageServiceConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of a StorageService.
StorageServiceSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a StorageService.
StorageSpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of a Storage.
StoredItem	Abstract representation of a stored data item within a storage resource.
SystemEnergy	Tracks overall power usage for entire systems or nodes, including CPU, memory, network, and storage subsystems.
SystemEnergyConfig	Represents the configurable parameters of SystemEnergy.
SystemEnergySpec	Defines the specification (capability characteristics) of SystemEnergy.
SystemMemory	Describes system memory, including capacity, performance, etc.
TelemetryInterface	Interface for exposing telemetry data from a resource, allowing for monitoring and observability integration.
ThermalSpecProfile	Describes thermal characteristics and cooling policies for a component, including max temperature and throttle thresholds.

Table 2: Overview of Resource model classes

A Table in Annex 10.2 provides a detailed view of all Resource model classes and attributes, including their data type.

7.2.3 Telemetry model

The Telemetry model provides a structured and extensible framework for representing runtime observability data across diverse components within the CCC. It is designed to capture, and

categorise telemetry data in a standardised manner, from compute, network, and other hardware or system-level sources. The model facilitates a unified view of system behaviour, facilitating dynamic decision-making, optimisation, and trust evaluation.

At the core of the model is the `Telemetry` abstraction, from which multiple specialised telemetry types inherit, each targeting a specific aspect of system monitoring. These include performance and utilisation (CPU, memory, network, storage, etc.), energy, thermal, environment, location, cognitive, orchestration (scheduler, workload, deployment state) and other telemetry domains. Metrics regarding the trust and security aspects have also been included to make the model more comprehensive. These telemetry subclasses are enriched with fields such as timestamps, particular metrics, confidence levels, and source identifiers enabling support for temporal data granularity, diverse measurement origins, and potential uncertainty via confidence indicators.

The `MeasurementValue` and `StatisticalValue` classes enable semantic distinction between concepts and observations. The meaning of the various metrics is defined via the relevant model classes and attributes in a more abstract manner, while the ones that take numerical values can be instantiated by means of these two classes, which allow for the specification of the value, unit of measurement, and measurement method. This allows for great flexibility, translatability of measurements and compatibility with different connected systems. While `MeasurementValue` class is used for capturing single numerical measurements, `StatisticalValue` is used for capturing parameters that are of statistical nature or associated with time (e.g., averages, such as throughput or other kinds of rates), also capturing the associated `TimeWindow`. Precision and confidence, wherever applicable, are captured by the `ObservationMetadata` class.

The structure is intentionally flexible to support integration with the configuration and specification aspects of the Resource model. Also taking into account the deployment goals set by means of the Application model, this facilitates alignment of runtime states with expected behaviour and deployment intent, further enabling self-adaptivity and optimisation, which are main objectives of the ENACT platform.

The UML diagram of the Telemetry model is presented in Figure 17. In this diagram, the `MeasurementValue` and `StatisticalValue` classes are intentionally not connected with other classes, to reduce the diagram complexity and ease its comprehension.

Figure 17: UML diagram of Telemetry model

Table 3 provides an overview of Telemetry model classes.

Class Name	Description
CPU Telemetry	Captures CPU-related telemetry metrics.
CPU Utilisation Telemetry	Captures runtime usage metrics and statistics regarding CPU utilisation.
Cognitive Drift Telemetry	Represents measurable deviations in the behaviour, performance, or internal consistency of intelligent systems, such as machine learning models, AI services, data pipelines, etc.
Cognitive Telemetry	Captures higher-level runtime insights regarding cognitive tasks, such as AI tasks and models training (e.g., intent, behaviour).
Deployment State Telemetry	Monitors the current deployment state of an application or service, including status codes or lifecycle stages.

DeviceTrustTelemetry	Captures trust-relevant runtime and contextual observations from devices, to inform whether a device is safe, compliant, and eligible to participate in workload execution, scheduling, or data exchange.
DriftTelemetry	Captures runtime drift between intended and actual configuration or behaviour of a system, helping detect misalignments or anomalies.
EnergyTelemetry	Reports energy consumption data and power-related metrics for hardware components or nodes.
EnvironmentTelemetry	Provides information about the conditions of the physical environment, such as humidity and vibration levels.
LearningTelemetry	Captures telemetry related to machine learning processes or models, such as training status, learning rate, or convergence indicators.
LocationTelemetry	Reports geolocation or spatial metadata, including node location, jurisdiction, or datacentre zone identifiers.
MeasurementValue	Enables a more abstract definition of all model attributes that take numerical values, and allows for the specification of their value, unit of measurement, and method measurement.
MemoryPressureTelemetry	Captures signals indicating stress on memory resources, such as usage nearing limits, increased paging activity, or allocation failures.
MemoryTelemetry	Captures memory-related telemetry metrics.
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	Captures runtime usage statistics and metrics related to memory utilisation.
ModelTelemetry	Describes runtime properties or performance characteristics of deployed AI/ML models (e.g. inference time, model version, accuracy).
NetworkTelemetry	Monitors network-related metrics such as latency and packet loss.
NetworkUtilisationTelemetry	Captures network utilisation runtime usage metrics statistics.
ObservationMetadata	A complementary class, used to define metadata of captured observations, such as precision and confidence level.
OrchestrationTelemetry	Captures telemetry related to orchestration systems, such as scheduling latency, queue depth, or decision events.
QueueMetric	Represents telemetry for system or orchestration queues and includes metrics such as queue length and average wait time.
SchedulerTelemetry	Reports scheduler-specific metrics such as failed scheduling attempts.
SecurityAndTrustTelemetry	Gathers trust and security indicators regarding user, device and workload.
StatisticalValue	Enables the precise definition of metrics that are statistically calculated or take into consideration the aspect of time, e.g. averages, throughput, etc.
StorageTelemetry	Captures storage-related telemetry metrics
StorageUtilisationTelemetry	Captures runtime usage metrics regarding storage.
TelemetryBase	The main class of the telemetry model, providing a timestamp as means of temporal granularity, an overall description of the measurement captured and its source.
TemperatureTelemetry	Reports raw or derived temperature readings from sensors attached to hardware components or the environment.
ThermalTelemetry	Aggregates thermal data for subsystems or entire nodes, potentially incorporating multiple sensor inputs and safety thresholds. Also, thermal-related properties, such as fan speed.
TimeWindow	Allows the definition of start and end datetime for time-dependent metrics.
TrustDriftTelemetry	Represents a measurable change in the trust posture of an entity over time. Relevant entities currently include users, devices or workflows.
TrustPolicyTelemetry	Captures the real-time or historical compliance status of an entity (user, device, workload) against one or more trust policies.

UserTrustTelemetry	Captures trust-relevant observations and signals about a user’s behaviour, context, and policy compliance, used to assess, score, and adjust trust in real time.
UtilisationTelemetry	A superclass aggregating runtime usage statistics for CPU, memory, network, storage and other components.
WorkloadTelemetry	Monitors workload-specific metrics, such as resource demands, runtime duration, or workload class/type identifiers.
WorkloadTrustTelemetry	Captures trust-relevant signals about deployed workloads, including their origin, integrity, policy compliance, and runtime behaviour, ensuring that workloads are authentic, secure, and executing within trusted boundaries.

Table 3: Overview of Telemetry model classes

A table in Annex 10.3 provides a detailed view of all Telemetry model classes and attributes, including their data type.

7.3 Development status (M18)

At M18 of the project, the first official version of the CCC Data Models has been successfully developed and made available in the consortium for facilitating components development and platform integration. The close collaboration among the consortium partners and the involvement of all ENACT component owners in the development process of the models, made sure that the various platform components developed at M18 were already compatible with the modelling framework introduced by the CCC Data Models.

In the next phase of the project (under WP7), the models will undergo further iterations and improvements as needed, based on findings collected during platform integration and pilot testing. Updates may include refinements such as updating specific data types or adding new parameters.

7.4 Relevant ENACT components and integration

This section briefly explains which of the developed CCC Data Models are utilised by each ENACT component and how.

7.4.1 Dynamic Graph Modeller

Resource Telemetry

The Dynamic Graph Modeller component utilises data from the Resource and Telemetry models, specifically regarding the identification of nodes and pods along with their status, connections and level of utilisation, to provide a near-real-time visualisation of the CCC.

7.4.2 Security Risk Modeller

Application Resource Telemetry

The Security Risk Modeller (SRM) component obtains information about structural and functional aspects of the system by means of the CCC Data Models. It evaluates application characteristics, including the type of application and data usage to ensure GDPR compliance, alongside infrastructure details such as the deployment configuration of Kubernetes clusters, including nodes, pods, and containers. Additionally, it incorporates resource models (covering node, network, and sensor capabilities) and telemetry data to identify deployed components. This integrated analysis enables SRM to provide a comprehensive evaluation of potential security risks.

7.4.3 Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine

Telemetry

The Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME) collects real-time metrics across the cloud continuum and undertakes the delivery of these metrics to other services without the need of a centralised storage point. These metrics include CPU and memory usage, disk load, network delay between nodes, pod-to-pod communication, and energy usage. Since distributed applications may operate on a diverse set of infrastructure setups, it is important to ensure that all metrics are transformed to a common format scheme. The TDCME is aligned with the Telemetry model, which formally defines the structure, nature, and associated value types of all collected telemetry data, in terms of metrics collected and their respective values.

7.4.4 Orchestrator

Application

The parameters of the Application Model can be used by the Orchestrator as a basis for application deployment. These parameters are included in the Deployment Plan description YAML in order to provide accurate deployment decisions made by the ENACT AI-Layer. The parameters of interest for these purposes include hardware requirements (RAM, CPU, hardware acceleration, etc.) needed to ensure the intended application performance, data storage, and network and security and privacy settings that orchestrator needs to have in consideration to ensure the provisioning and configuration of the needed resources.

While the Orchestrator requires information regarding the resources on the cluster and their status to accurately perform the needed deployment actions, it does not use the corresponding CCC Models to represent this information internally. This is due to the fact the Orchestrator already has direct access to the cluster and the relevant information, hence being preferable to adhere to the format used by the cluster to consume this information, as long as it is only being used internally by the Orchestrator component. Moreover, and since the accuracy of information to describe the current state of the cluster is essential to perform the deployment, it is important to reduce the delay of between the time of data collection and its use by the orchestrator.

7.4.5 AI Forecaster

Telemetry

The AI Forecaster component utilises data from the Telemetry model to forecast network data, detect anomalies and propose a plan to allocate computing resources across the continuum. The metrics mainly used concern node, pod and container identification, resources utilisation, energy consumption, network performance, and node health.

7.4.6 Application Controller

Application Telemetry

The Application Controller component monitors and collects application metrics to dynamically realise and implement application adaptation mechanisms based on feedback from the environment or user preferences. From the Telemetry model, it utilises parameters such as node and pod identification, resources utilisation/load and energy consumption. From the Application Model, the Application Controller will make use of attributes used and referenced by the Application Policy Model, when checking for and requesting adaptation actions.

7.4.7 Application Programming Model

Application Resource Telemetry

The Application Programming Model provides a set of libraries to build applications and services to be deployed to the CCC, which include characteristics such as dynamism, adaptation, elasticity, load balancing, replication, portability, identification, secure communication, self-registering, etc. It exposes the APIs of various ENACT components, and hence utilises all three CCC Models indirectly. Additionally, it utilises the Application model for obtaining application-specific details application (libraries version, changelog, known limitations, legacy support) and deployment requirements (software/hardware) and the Telemetry model to track resource utilisation and exceptions/errors.

7.4.8 AI Act Compliance Check

Application

The Artificial Intelligence part of the Application model was created based on the feedback received from the AI Act Compliance Check component developers. Hence, the Application model could serve as a means for application owners or providers to provide AI-related information in future iterations.

7.4.9 Application Policy Model

Application

The Application Policy Model is an implementation of the corresponding CCC Model. The Application Policy Model is offered as a Kubernetes operator whereas a Custom Resource Definition is created that provides distributed application developers a means of defining the desired runtime behaviour of the applications following cloud native practices. Through the Application Policy Model, developers can express compute, networking, storage and security characteristics of distributed applications.

7.4.10 Data Manager

Application Resource Telemetry

The developed ENACT CCC models provide a standardised way for expressing data across the ENACT ecosystem, facilitating seamless interoperability and consistency in data representation. Consequently, all ENACT data assets are represented using the defined application, resource and telemetry models and distributed throughout the ENACT CCC via the ENACT Data Space. Besides providing distributed data storage, the Data Space layer also fosters alignment with the established data models. By supporting the definition of pertinent data asset fields, it ensures that each data type - whether it being telemetry metrics, resource descriptors or application-level data - can be structured according to its respective ENACT model, hence contributing to the exchange of data assets in a consistent manner within the ENACT ecosystem.

8. Release Summary

Component	Subcomponent	Release Information	Details and Links
Dynamic Graph Modeller	Backend	Version	1.0.1
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/dynamic-graph-modeller/-/tree/main/src/dgm-be?ref_type=heads
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/dynamic-graph-modeller/-/blob/main/README.md?ref_type=heads
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	Telemetry Data Collector and Monitor Engine (TDCME)
	Frontend	Version	1.0.1
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/dynamic-graph-modeller/-/tree/main/src/dgm-fe?ref_type=heads
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/dynamic-graph-modeller/-/tree/main/src/dgm-fe?ref_type=heads
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	Subcomponent Backend

Table 4: Summary table of Dynamic Graph Modeller release information

Component	Subcomponent	Release Information	Details and Links
CCC Data Models	Application Model	Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/ccc-models/-/blob/main/application-model/Application_Model_v1.0.puml
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/ccc-models/-/blob/main/README.md
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	-
	Resource Model	Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/ccc-models/-/blob/main/resource-model/Resource_Model_v1.0.puml
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/ccc-models/-/blob/main/README.md
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	-
	Telemetry Model	Version	1.0.0
		Source Code	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/ccc-models/-/blob/main/telemetry-model/Telemetry_Model_v1.0.puml
		Binaries	-
		Documentation	https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/enact-project/ccc-models/-/blob/main/README.md
		Docker Image	-
		Dependencies	-

Table 5: Summary table of CCC Data Model release information

9. Conclusions

This deliverable presents the design and implementation of two key components of the ENACT platform, namely, the CCC Data Models and the Dynamic Graph Modeller. A summary of the open-source release of these components is also provided in this document.

The DGM collects metrics from the Orchestration Layer and constructs a graph representation of the continuum that captures the key relationships between the different elements, as well as their operational status. This graph serves as an input for other components of the ENACT platform. In addition, the DGM provides a user interface to visualize the graph, highlighting the most relevant information for the users.

Regarding the CCC Data Models, they have been defined based on an exhaustive analysis of the needs of the system components and end-users and aim to enable a standardized representation of the data from the continuum in order to allow automatic processing by the ENACT platform components. The CCC Data Models contain three main models, namely, the Application/Service Model, the Resource/Device Model and the Telemetry Model.

During the second part of the project, as part of WP7 efforts, these components will be integrated into the pilots and improvements will be made based on the feedback received from the end-users.

10. Annex

10.1 Application model details

As mentioned before, one of the Application Model purposes is the definition of deployment goals for applications and services in the CCC. Also, it should be able to accommodate interaction with various types of users and levels of expertise, ranging, e.g., from human operators to customised software components. When used for high-level description purposes (e.g., expression of deployment goals by a human user), some of the model's classes could be instantiated as attributes to describe the desired level of accomplishment of a particular concept/domain. E.g., `AcceptableApproximation` class could be considered an attribute and instantiated with the value "High precision", which is more conversational than technical, for indicating that tight tolerance is required. Otherwise, the attributes `ConfidenceLevel` and/or `ErrorMargin` could be used for more precise and technical definition of the relevant requirements.

Table 6 presents in detail all classes and attributes of the Application model. It also includes references to sub-classes, marked with the term "Class" in the table, in particular to facilitate the understanding of the Artificial Intelligence domain of the Application Model, which has been visualised in section 7.2.1, albeit its specifics may be difficult to discern in the relevant figure.

Class Name	Attribute	Type
AcceptableApproximation	ConfidenceLevel	Attribute
AcceptableApproximation	ErrorMargin	Attribute
Accuracy	AcceptableApproximation	Class
Application	ArtificialIntelligence	Class
Application	DataStorage	Class
Application	DataTransfer	Class
Application	Deployment	Class
Application	Details	Class
Application	EnergyAndCost	Class
Application	Network	Class
Application	OtherTechnicalDetails	Class
Application	Performance	Class
Application	SecurityAndPrivacy	Class
Application	ServiceLevel	Class
Application	UsageDemand	Class
AuthorisationAndAccessControl	Token	Class
Availability	RecoveryMean-time	Attribute
Availability	Up-time	Attribute
Bandwidth	Download	Attribute
Bandwidth	Upload	Attribute
CPU	Cores	Class
CPU	Family	Attribute
CPU	Instructions	Attribute
Cores	Max	Attribute
Cores	Min	Attribute
Cost	Computation	Attribute

Cost	DataAccess	Attribute
Cost	DataStorage	Class
Cost	Overall	Class
DataEncryption	Algorithm	Attribute
DataEncryption	Parameters	Attribute
DataObject	ObjectFormat	Attribute
DataObject	ObjectType	Attribute
DataRetrieval	AcceptableAmount	Attribute
DataStorage	AcceptableAmount	Attribute
DataStorage	ContentType	Attribute
DataStorage	DataObject	Class
DataStorage	Freshness	Class
DataStorage	Index	Attribute
DataStorage	Latency	Class
DataStorage	Location	Class
DataStorage	Owner	Attribute
DataStorage	Size	Attribute
DataStorage	SourceApplication	Attribute
DataStorage	StorageDevice	Class
DataStorage	TimePeriod	Class
DataTransfer	InputData	Class
DataTransfer	OutputData	Class
Deployment	Duration	Class
Deployment	Environment	Attribute
Deployment	ReplicasNumber	Attribute
Details	Endpoint	Attribute
Details	Id	Attribute
Details	Name	Attribute
Details	Type	Class
Development	ProgrammingLanguage	Attribute
Duration	Overall	Class
Duration	Scheduled	Class
Energy	Consumption	Attribute
EnergyAndCost	Cost	Class
EnergyAndCost	Energy	Class
EraseCoding	RedundancyLevel	Attribute
EraseCoding	Scheme	Attribute
EraseCoding	StripeSize	Attribute
Execution	ResponseLatency	Attribute
Execution	TotalExecutionTime	Attribute
ExecutionEnvironment	OperatingSystem	Attribute
ExecutionEnvironment	SoftwareDependencies	Class
ExecutionEnvironment	SoftwareEnvironment	Class
Freshness	Age	Attribute
Freshness	LastUpdated	Attribute
GeographicalLocation	Country	Attribute
GeographicalLocation	ResidesInTheEU	Attribute

HardwareAcceleration	Type	Class
InputData	Size	Attribute
InputData	TypeOrCategory	Attribute
Latency	DataRetrieval	Class
Latency	DataStorage	Class
Location	GeographicalLocation	Class
Location	On-premiseStorage	Attribute
Network	NetworkCapacity	Class
NetworkCapacity	Bandwidth	Class
NetworkCapacity	Jitter	Attribute
NetworkCapacity	Latency	Class
OtherTechnicalDetails	Development	Class
OtherTechnicalDetails	ExecutionEnvironment	Class
OutputData	Size	Attribute
OutputData	TypeOrCategory	Attribute
Overall	EndDateTime	Attribute
Overall	StartDateTime	Attribute
Performance	CPU	Class
Performance	Execution	Class
Performance	HardwareAcceleration	Class
Performance	Parallelisation	Attribute
Performance	RAM	Class
Privacy	DataNature	Attribute
RAM	RAMCapacity	Class
RAM	Timing	Class
RAM	Type	Class
RAMCapacity	Max	Attribute
RAMCapacity	Min	Attribute
Range	EndDateTime	Attribute
Range	StartDateTime	Attribute
Reliability	FailureRate	Attribute
Reliability	OverallReliability	Attribute
RequestsNumber	ConcurrentRequestsNumber	Attribute
RequestsNumber	TotalRequestsNumber	Attribute
Scaling	InstancesNumber	Attribute
Scheduled	EndDateTime	Attribute
Scheduled	StartDateTime	Attribute
Security	DataEncryption	Class
Security	ErasureCoding	Class
SecurityAndPrivacy	AuthorisationAndAccessControl	Class
SecurityAndPrivacy	LegalFramework	Attribute
SecurityAndPrivacy	Privacy	Class
SecurityAndPrivacy	Security	Class
ServiceLevel	Accuracy	Class
ServiceLevel	Availability	Class
ServiceLevel	Reliability	Class
SoftwareDependencies	LibrariesOrFrameworks	Attribute

SoftwareEnvironment	RuntimeOrExecutionEnvironment	Attribute
StorageDevice	Category	Attribute
StorageDevice	Type	Class
TimePeriod	Duration	Class
TimePeriod	Range	Class
Timinng	Number	Attribute
Token	Format	Attribute
Token	Id	Attribute
Token	Response	Attribute
Type	DPU	Attribute
Type	FPGA	Attribute
Type	GPU	Attribute
Type	NIC	Attribute
Type	OtherHardware	Attribute
UsageDemand	UseFrequency	Class
UsageDemand	Scaling	Class
UsageDemand	TimePeriod	Class
UsageDemand	Users	Class
UseFrequency	RequestsNumber	Class
Users	UsersNumber	Class
UsersNumber	ConcurrentUsersNumber	Attribute
UsersNumber	TotalUsersPerTimePeriod	Attribute
Artificial Intelligence domain		
ArtificialIntelligence	AISystemDevelopmentProcess	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	AdversarialTestingModelAdaptation	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	DetailedDescriptionGeneral	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	EUDeclarationConformity	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	EvaluationStrategies	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	GeneralDescription	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	HarmonisedStandards	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	LifecycleChanges	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	MonitoringFunctioningControl	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	PerformanceMetrics	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	PostMarketMonitoring	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	RiskManagement	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	SystemArchitecture	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	CybersecurityMeasures	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	DataRequirementsAndMethodologies	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	DesignSpecifications	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	HumanOversightAndInterpretability	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	Pre-DeterminedChangesAndContinuousCompliance	Attribute
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	Process	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	SystemArchitecture	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	ValidationAndTesting	Class
AISystemDevelopmentProcess	SystemDevelopmentAppendices	Class

AccuracyLevels	OverallExpectedAccuracy	Attribute
AccuracyLevels	SpecificAccuracyLevels	Attribute
AccuracyRobustnessAndCybersecurity		Attribute
AdditionalInformation	ExemptionsOrConditions	Attribute
AdditionalInformation	TestingMethods	Attribute
AdditionalStandards	ApplicationDetails	Attribute
AdditionalStandards	ApplicationPurpose	Attribute
AdditionalStandards	Reference	Attribute
AdditionalStandards	Title	Attribute
AdoptedSolutions	AccuracyRobustnessAndCybersecurity(Article15)	Attribute
AdoptedSolutions	DataAndDataGovernance(Article10)	Attribute
AdoptedSolutions	HumanOversight(Article14)	Attribute
AdoptedSolutions	Record-Keeping(Article12)	Attribute
AdoptedSolutions	RiskManagementSystem(Article9)	Attribute
AdoptedSolutions	TechnicalDocumentation(Article11)	Attribute
AdoptedSolutions	TransparencyAndInformationProvision(Article13)	Attribute
AdversarialTestingModelAdaptation	EvaluationMetrics	Class
AdversarialTestingModelAdaptation	ExternalAdversarialTesting	Class
AdversarialTestingModelAdaptation	InternalAdversarialTesting	Class
AdversarialTestingModelAdaptation	ModelAdaptations	Class
ApplicabilityToSpecificUserGroupsOrEnvironments	VulnerableGroupsConsiderations	Attribute
ApplicabilityToSpecificUserGroupsOrEnvironments	Demographic-SpecificPerformance	Attribute
ArchitecturalComponents	CoreProcessingEngine	Class
ArchitecturalComponents	InputLayer	Class
ArchitecturalComponents	OutputLayer	Class
ArchitecturalComponents	PreprocessingModule	Class
ArchitecturalPrinciples	FaultTolerance	Attribute
ArchitecturalPrinciples	Modularity	Attribute
ArchitecturalPrinciples	Scalability	Attribute
ArchitectureOverview	ArchitecturalPrinciples	Class
ArchitectureOverview	ArchitectureDiagrams	Attribute
ArchitectureOverview	ComponentInteractionAndIntegration	Attribute
ArtificialIntelligence	AISystemDevelopmentProcess	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	AdversarialTestingModelAdaptation	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	DetailedDescriptionGeneral	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	EUDeclarationConformity	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	EvaluationStrategies	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	GeneralDescription	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	HarmonisedStandards	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	LifecycleChanges	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	MonitoringFunctioningControl	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	PerformanceMetrics	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	PostMarketMonitoring	Class
ArtificialIntelligence	RiskManagement	Class

ArtificialIntelligence	SystemArchitecture	Class
Attachments	SupportingDocuments	Class
AttachmentsAndSupportingDocuments	SupportingDocumentation	Attribute
BiasAndFairnessMeasures	BiasMonitoringTools	Attribute
BiasAndFairnessMeasures	DataSamplingAndBalance	Attribute
CapabilitiesAndLimitations	MFCLimitations	Class
CapabilitiesAndLimitations	PerformanceCapabilities	Class
Change	ChangeNr	Attribute
Change	ImplementationDate	Attribute
Change	TheChangeDescription	Attribute
Change	EffectOnRiskProfile	Attribute
Change	SystemPerformancelmpact	Attribute
Change	TheChangeReason	Attribute
Change	StakeholderCommunication	Attribute
Change	TestingAndValidation	Attribute
Change	ChangeType	Attribute
Change	VersionNumber	Attribute
ChangeImpactSummary	ChangesCumulativeImpact	Class
ChangeImpactSummary	UpdatedRiskAssessment	Class
ChangeLogOverview	ChangesTypes	Attribute
ChangesCumulativeImpact	OperationalScopeChanges	Attribute
ChangesCumulativeImpact	Performancelmprovements	Attribute
ChangesSummary	ChangeLogOverview	Class
ComputationalResources	TrainingDuration	Attribute
ComputationalResources	TrainingHardware	Attribute
ConformityStatement	ReferencedLegislation	Attribute
ContinuousMonitoring	AnomalyDetectionMethods	Attribute
ContinuousMonitoring	Real-TimeOrPeriodicChecks	Attribute
CoreProcessingEngine	LayerDetails	Attribute
CoreProcessingEngine	NeuralNetworkType	Attribute
CoreProcessingEngine	ParameterOverview	Attribute
CybersecurityMeasures	RiskAssessment	Class
CybersecurityMeasures	SecurityProtocols	Class
DataAnalysis	AnalysisObjectives	Attribute
DataAnalysis	AnalysisMethods	Attribute
DataAndDataGovernance(Article10)	DataQualityAndGovernancePractices	Attribute
DataCollection	DataSources	Attribute
DataCollection	DataTypes	Attribute
DataRequirementsAndConstraints	DataCompatibility	Attribute
DataRequirementsAndConstraints	MinimumDataQuality	Attribute
DataRequirementsAndMethodologies	BiasAndFairnessMeasures	Class
DataRequirementsAndMethodologies	TrainingDatashets	Class
DataRequirementsAndMethodologies	TrainingData	Class
DataSetsUsed	TrainingData	Class
DataSetsUsed	ValidationAndTestingData	Attribute
DataUsed	BiasDetectionMeasures	Attribute
DataUsed	DataCuration	Attribute

DataUsed	DataTypesAndSources	Attribute
DataUsed	SizeAndScope	Attribute
DeployersCommunication	FeedbackChannels	Attribute
DeployersCommunication	ResponseProcedures	Attribute
DeploymentFormats	DeploymentForms	Attribute
DeploymentFormats	UpdateAndMaintenance	Class
DeploymentInstructions	ConfigurationOptions	Attribute
DeploymentInstructions	InstallationSteps	Attribute
DeploymentInstructions	IntegrationProcesses	Attribute
DeploymentScale	ExpectedUserBase	Attribute
DeploymentScale	GeographicReach	Attribute
DesignAndTrainingProcess	ArchitectureOverview	Class
DesignAndTrainingProcess	DesignDecisions	Attribute
DesignAndTrainingProcess	OptimizationGoals	Class
DesignAndTrainingProcess	ParameterRelevance	Attribute
DesignAndTrainingProcess	TrainingMethodology	Attribute
DesignChoices	ClassificationChoices	Attribute
DesignChoices	IntendedUsersAndGroups	Class
DesignChoices	KeyDesignDecisions	Class
DesignSpecifications	DesignChoices	Class
DesignSpecifications	ExpectedOutputsAndOutputQuality	Class
DesignSpecifications	GeneralLogicAndAlgorithms	Class
DesignSpecifications	OptimizationGoals	Class
DesignSpecifications	Trade-Offs	Class
DetailedChangeDescriptions	Changes	List<Change >
DetailedDescriptionGeneral	ComputationalResources	Class
DetailedDescriptionGeneral	DataUsed	Class
DetailedDescriptionGeneral	DesignAndTrainingProcess	Class
DetailedDescriptionGeneral	EnergyConsumption	Class
DetailedDescriptionGeneral	IntegrationToolsAndInfrastructure	Class
DevelopmentAssumptions	DesignBiasesOrLimitations	Attribute
DevelopmentAssumptions	AssumptionsAboutTheOperatingEnvironment	Attribute
DevelopmentAssumptions	ExpectedUserBehavior	Attribute
DevelopmentMethodsAndSteps	KeyMilestonesAndDecisionPoints	Attribute
DevelopmentMethodsAndSteps	MethodologiesUsed	Attribute
DevelopmentMethodsAndSteps	StepsInTheDevelopmentLifecycle	Attribute
DevelopmentMethodsAndSteps	Pre-TrainedSystemsOrToolsUse	Class
DevelopmentResources	Cloud-BasedToolsOrEnvironments	Attribute
DevelopmentResources	HardwareAndSoftwareUsed	Attribute
EUDeclarationConformity	AdditionalInformation	Class
EUDeclarationConformity	ConformityStatement	Class
EUDeclarationConformity	HarmonisedStandardsOrSpecificationsUsed	Class
EUDeclarationConformity	ManufacturerInformation	Class
EUDeclarationConformity	NotifiedBodyInformation	Class
EUDeclarationConformity	TheDeclarationObject	Class
EUDeclarationConformity	ProductIdentification	Class

EUDeclarationConformity	SignatureBlock	Class
EUDeclarationConformity	SoleResponsibilityStatement	Class
EnergyConsumption	EstimatedOrMeasuredEnergyUse	Attribute
EvaluatingPerformanceMetricsMethodology	DataSetsUsed	Class
EvaluatingPerformanceMetricsMethodology	TestingProcedures	Class
EvaluatingPerformanceMetricsMethodology	ThresholdsAndBenchmarks	Class
EvaluationCriteria	Accuracy	Attribute
EvaluationCriteria	BiasDetection	Attribute
EvaluationCriteria	Efficiency	Attribute
EvaluationCriteria	Robustness	Attribute
EvaluationLimitations	BiasAudits	Attribute
EvaluationLimitations	ErrorAnalysis	Attribute
EvaluationLimitations	PerformanceMonitoring	Attribute
EvaluationMethodology	Benchmarks	Attribute
EvaluationMethodology	Cross-Validation	Attribute
EvaluationMethodology	UserStudies	Attribute
EvaluationMetrics	BiasLevels	Attribute
EvaluationMetrics	MetricTypes	Class
EvaluationMetrics	RobustnessMetrics	Attribute
EvaluationMetrics	UserSatisfactionScores	Attribute
EvaluationResults	ImprovementStrategies	Attribute
EvaluationResults	FindingsSummary	Attribute
EvaluationStrategies	EvaluationCriteria	Class
EvaluationStrategies	EvaluationMethodology	Class
EvaluationStrategies	EvaluationMetrics	Class
EvaluationStrategies	EvaluationResults	Class
EvaluationStrategies	EvaluationLimitations	Class
ExistingMonitoringSystemsIntegration	InternalOrRegulatoryFrameworks	Attribute
ExpectedOutputsAndOutputQuality	MonitoringMechanisms	Attribute
ExpectedOutputsAndOutputQuality	QualityBenchmarks	Attribute
ExpectedOutputsAndOutputQuality	SystemOutputDescriptions	Attribute
ExternalAdversarialTesting	BugBountyPrograms	Attribute
ExternalAdversarialTesting	Third-PartyAudits	Attribute
ExternalSystemsIntegration	APIInterfaces	Attribute
ExternalSystemsInteraction	HardwareOrSoftwareInteractions	Class
ForeseeableUnintendedOutcomes	BiasOrInequityRisks	Attribute
ForeseeableUnintendedOutcomes	RisksToHealthSafetyOrRights	Attribute
ForeseeableUnintendedOutcomes	UnintendedConsequences	Attribute
GeneralAppendices	AdditionalResources	Attribute
GeneralAppendices	DiagramsAndIllustrations	Attribute
GeneralAppendices	Glossary	Attribute
GeneralDescription	GeneralAppendices	Class
GeneralDescription	DeploymentFormats	Class
GeneralDescription	HardwareRequirements	Class
GeneralDescription	UseInstructions	Class
GeneralDescription	IntegrationIntoProducts	Class
GeneralDescription	ExternalSystemsInteraction	Class

GeneralDescription	Introduction	Class
GeneralDescription	SoftwareAndFirmwareDetails	Class
GeneralDescription	SystemDescription	Class
GeneralDescription	UserInterface	Class
GeneralFunctionality	ExternalSystemDependencies	Attribute
GeneralFunctionality	ModelTypesUsed	Attribute
GeneralFunctionality	TaskPerformance	Attribute
GeneralLogicAndAlgorithms	AISystemAndAlgorithmsHigh-LevelFunctionality	Attribute
GeneralLogicAndAlgorithms	WorkflowsOverview	Attribute
GeneralLogicAndAlgorithms	PrimaryAlgorithms/modelsUsed	Attribute
GeneralLogicAndAlgorithms	AlgorithmsInTheSystemRoles	Attribute
HardwareOrSoftwareInteractions	CommunicationProtocols/interfaces	Attribute
HardwareOrSoftwareInteractions	OtherAISystemsInteractions	Attribute
HardwareOrSoftwareInteractions	SystemDependencies	Attribute
HardwareRequirements	SupportedHardware	Class
HarmonisedStandards	AdoptedSolutions	Class
HarmonisedStandards	Attachments	Class
HarmonisedStandards	HarmonisedStandardsApplied	Class
HarmonisedStandards	OtherStandardsAndTechnicalSpecificationsApplied	Class
HarmonisedStandardsApplied	StandardReferenceEntries	Class
HarmonisedStandardsOrSpecificationsUsed	StandardsList	Attribute
HumanInterventionAndControl	InterpretationSupport	Attribute
HumanInterventionAndControl	OverrideMechanisms	Class
HumanOversight(Article14)	OversightMechanisms	Attribute
HumanOversightAndInterpretability	InterpretabilityMeasures	Class
HumanOversightAndInterpretability	OversightMeasures	Class
HumanOversightMeasures	HumanInterventionAndControl	Class
HumanOversightMeasures	OversightMechanisms	Class
HumanOversightMeasures	TechnicalMeasures	Class
InformationAndTrainingProvision	DeployersInformation	Attribute
InformationAndTrainingProvision	DeployersTraining	Attribute
Infrastructure	Cloud/on-PremRequirements	Attribute
Infrastructure	Hardware/softwareDependencies	Attribute
InputDataDescription	PreprocessingSteps	Attribute
InputDataDescription	DataUsedType	Attribute
InputDataSpecifications	DataRequirementsAndConstraints	Class
InputDataSpecifications	InputDataDescription	Class
InputLayer	DataCollectionMethods	Attribute
InputLayer	InitialProcessingTechniques	Attribute
IntegrationIntoProducts	ProductIntegration	Class
IntegrationToolsAndInfrastructure	Infrastructure	Class
IntegrationToolsAndInfrastructure	Tools	Class
IntendedPurpose	ApplicationsOrIndustries	Attribute
IntendedPurpose	ProblemAddressed	Attribute
IntendedPurpose	UseScope	Attribute

IntendedPurpose	UseCasesAndAudience	Attribute
IntendedUseCasesAlignment	IndustryStandards	Attribute
IntendedUseCasesAlignment	RelevanceToSystemPurpose	Attribute
IntendedUseCasesAlignment	UseCaseExamples	Attribute
IntendedUsersAndGroups	ExclusionRationale	Attribute
IntendedUsersAndGroups	TargetUserGroups	Attribute
InteractionMechanisms	SoftwareInteractions	Attribute
InternalAdversarialTesting	AdversarialInputCrafting	Attribute
InternalAdversarialTesting	MaliciousInputHandling	Attribute
InterpretabilityMeasures	OutputExplainabilityFeatures	Attribute
Introduction	Purpose	Class
KeyDesignDecisions	DevelopmentAssumptions	Class
KeyDesignDecisions	Model/Framework/DatasetSelectionRationale	Attribute
KeyDesignDecisions	KeyDesignChoicesRationale	Attribute
LifecycleAppendices	Glossary	Attribute
LifecycleAppendices	TestingReports	Attribute
LifecycleAppendices	StakeholderNotifications	Attribute
LifecycleChanges	LifecycleAppendices	Class
LifecycleChanges	ChangeImpactSummary	Class
LifecycleChanges	DetailedChangeDescriptions	Class
LifecycleChanges	ChangesSummary	Class
LifecycleChanges	VersionHistoryTable	Class
MFCAppendices	Glossary	Attribute
MFCAppendices	AdditionalResources	Attribute
MFCAppendices	IllustrationsAndDiagrams	Attribute
MFLimitations	EnvironmentalOrOperationalConstraints	Attribute
MFLimitations	KnownLimitations	Attribute
ManufacturerInformation	Address	Attribute
ManufacturerInformation	Name	Attribute
MetricTypes	F1Score	Attribute
MetricTypes	MeanAveragePrecision	Attribute
MetricTypes	OtherRelevantMetrics	Attribute
MetricsAdaptation	UseCaseChangesOrStandardsAdaptation	Attribute
MetricsAdaptation	UpdateProcedures	Attribute
MetricsAndResults	Accuracy	Attribute
MetricsAndResults	Compliance	Attribute
MetricsAndResults	Robustness	Attribute
MetricsAndResults	TestLogs	Attribute
MetricsLimitations	KnownLimitations	Attribute
MetricsLimitations	SupplementaryMethodsToAddressLimitations	Attribute
ModelAdaptations	BiasMitigationTechniques	Attribute
ModelAdaptations	EthicalAlignment	Attribute
ModelAdaptations	Fine-TuningProcedures	Attribute
ModelAdaptations	UserFeedbackIntegration	Attribute
ModelAndPerformanceCharacteristics	ModelReach	Attribute
ModelAndPerformanceCharacteristics	ParametersNumber	Attribute
ModelAndPerformanceCharacteristics	TrainingDataOverview	Attribute

MonitoringActivities	KeyMonitoringActionsAndFrequency	Attribute
MonitoringAndUpdatingMetrics	MetricsAdaptation	Class
MonitoringAndUpdatingMetrics	ContinuousMonitoring	Class
MonitoringFunctioningControl	MFCAppendices	Class
MonitoringFunctioningControl	CapabilitiesAndLimitations	Class
MonitoringFunctioningControl	HumanOversightMeasures	Class
MonitoringFunctioningControl	InputDataSpecifications	Class
MonitoringFunctioningControl	RiskManagement	Class
NotifiedBodyInformation	CertificateReference	Attribute
NotifiedBodyInformation	InterventionDescription	Attribute
NotifiedBodyInformation	NameAndNumber	Attribute
Objectives	EthicalAIPromotion	Attribute
Objectives	FundamentalRightsProtection	Attribute
Objectives	SafetyAssurance	Attribute
OptimizationGoals	OptimizationObjectivesDefinition	Attribute
OptimizationGoals	RelevantParameters	Class
OtherRiskManagementProcessesIntegration	OtherRegulatoryRequirementsAlignment	Attribute
OtherStandardsAndTechnicalSpecificationsApplied	AdditionalStandards	Class
OutputLayer	OutputChannels	Attribute
OutputLayer	PredictionFormat	Attribute
OverrideMechanisms	EmergencyProcedures	Attribute
OverrideMechanisms	ManualOverrideOptions	Attribute
OversightMeasures	HumanOversightProcedures	Attribute
OversightMechanisms	MeasuresOverview	Attribute
Overview	SystemObjectives	Attribute
PerformanceAppendices	MetricsGlossary	Attribute
PerformanceAppendices	References	Attribute
PerformanceCapabilities	AccuracyLevels	Class
PerformanceCapabilities	GeneralPerformance	Attribute
PerformanceMetrics	SystemContextMetricsAppropriateness	Class
PerformanceMetrics	EvaluatingPerformanceMetricsMethodology	Class
PerformanceMetrics	MonitoringAndUpdatingMetrics	Class
PerformanceMetrics	PerformanceMetricsOverview	Class
PerformanceMetrics	PerformanceAppendices	Class
PerformanceMetricsOverview	SelectedMetrics	Class
PlannedChanges	ComplianceMechanisms	Attribute
PlannedChanges	ScheduledUpdates	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringSystemDescription	DataAnalysis	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringSystemDescription	DataCollection	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringSystemDescription	ExistingMonitoringSystemsIntegration	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringSystemDescription	Overview	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringPlan	DeployersCommunication	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringPlan	SystemPerformanceEvaluation	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringPlan	MonitoringActivities	Attribute
Post-MarketMonitoringPlan	RiskAssessment	Attribute
PostMarketMonitoring	AttachmentsAndSupportingDocuments	Class

PostMarketMonitoring	Post-MarketMonitoringSystemDescription	Class
PostMarketMonitoring	Post-MarketMonitoringPlan	Class
PostMarketMonitoring	ReportingAndCompliance	Class
Pre-DeterminedChangesAndContinuousCompliance	PlannedChanges	Class
Pre-TrainedSystemsOrToolsUse	Integration	Attribute
Pre-TrainedSystemsOrToolsUse	Source	Attribute
PreprocessingModule	DataTransformationMethods	Attribute
PrimaryMetrics	Definitions	Attribute
PrimaryMetrics	KeyPerformanceMetrics	Attribute
Process	DevelopmentMethodsAndSteps	Class
ProductIdentification	UniqueProductNumber	Attribute
ProductIntegration	MarkingAndLayout	Attribute
ProductIntegration	PhotographsOrIllustrations	Attribute
Purpose	IntendedPurpose	Class
Purpose	ProviderName	Attribute
Purpose	SystemName	Attribute
Purpose	Version	Attribute
Record-Keeping(Article12)	TraceabilitySystem	Attribute
RelevantParameters	ParameterRolesAndPerformanceImpact	Attribute
RelevantParameters	ParameterTuningAndMonitoring	Attribute
ReportingAndCompliance	InternalReporting	Attribute
ReportingAndCompliance	Record-Keeping	Attribute
ReportingAndCompliance	SubmissionToAuthorities	Attribute
ResidualRisks	Post-MitigationRiskOverview	Attribute
RiskAssessment	CybersecurityRiskEvaluation	Attribute
RiskAssessment	RiskIdentification	Attribute
RiskAssessment	RiskMitigationMeasures	Class
RiskCategories	KnownRisks	Attribute
RiskCategories	ReasonablyForeseeableRisks	Attribute
RiskEstimationAndEvaluation	ResidualRisks	Class
RiskEstimationAndEvaluation	RiskEvaluationCriteria	Class
RiskEvaluationCriteria	AcceptanceThresholds	Attribute
RiskEvaluationCriteria	LikelihoodAndSeverity	Attribute
RiskIdentificationAndAnalysis	RiskCategories	Class
RiskIdentificationAndAnalysis	RiskIdentificationProcess	Class
RiskIdentificationProcess	Methodology	Attribute
RiskIdentificationProcess	Scope	Attribute
RiskManagemenAppendices	Glossary	Attribute
RiskManagemenAppendices	RiskMatrix	Attribute
RiskManagemenAppendices	References	Attribute
RiskManagement	VulnerableGroupsConsideration	Class
RiskManagement	ForeseeableUnintendedOutcomes	Class
RiskManagement	OtherRiskManagementProcessesIntegration	Class
RiskManagement	RiskManagementSystemOverview	Class
RiskManagement	RiskEstimationAndEvaluation	Class

RiskManagement	RiskIdentificationAndAnalysis	Class
RiskManagement	RiskManagementMeasures	Class
RiskManagement	RiskMitigationMeasures	Class
RiskManagement	RiskSources	Class
RiskManagement	Testing	Class
RiskManagement	RiskeManagementAppendices	Attribute
RiskManagementFramework	FrameworkDescription	Attribute
RiskManagementFramework	LifecycleIntegration	Attribute
RiskManagementMeasures	InformationAndTrainingProvision	Class
RiskManagementMeasures	RiskMitigationStrategies	Class
RiskManagementSystem(Article9)	ProcessesAndMethodologies	Attribute
RiskManagementSystemOverview	Objectives	Class
RiskManagementSystemOverview	RiskManagementFramework	Class
RiskMitigationMeasures	MonitoringAndResponse	Attribute
RiskMitigationMeasures	PreventionStrategies	Attribute
RiskMitigationStrategies	DesignAndDevelopmentMeasures	Attribute
RiskMitigationStrategies	MitigationAndControlMeasures	Attribute
RiskSources	ContextualMisuse	Attribute
RiskSources	DataQuality	Attribute
RiskSources	ModelLimitations	Attribute
SAComputationalResources	DevelopmentResources	Class
SAComputationalResources	TestingAndValidationResources	Attribute
SAComputationalResources	TrainingResources	Attribute
SecondaryMetrics	SupplementaryMetrics	Attribute
SecurityProtocols	EncryptionAndAccessControl	Attribute
SecurityProtocols	MonitoringSystems	Attribute
SecurityProtocols	ThreatMitigation	Attribute
SelectedMetrics	PrimaryMetrics	Class
SelectedMetrics	SecondaryMetrics	Class
SignatureBlock	IssueDate	Attribute
SignatureBlock	SignatoryNameAndTitle	Attribute
SignatureBlock	IssuePlace	Attribute
SignatureBlock	Signature	Attribute
Software/firmwareVersions	SupportedVersions	Attribute
Software/firmwareVersions	UpdateRequirements	Attribute
SoftwareAndFirmwareDetails	Software/firmwareVersions	Class
SoleResponsibilityStatement	DeclarationStatement	Attribute
StandardReferenceEntries	ApplicationScope	Attribute
StandardReferenceEntries	ImplementationDetails	Attribute
StandardReferenceEntries	Reference	Attribute
StandardReferenceEntries	TheStandardTitle	Attribute
SupportedHardware	MinimumRequirements	Attribute
SupportedHardware	RecommendedConfigurations	Attribute
SupportingDocuments	ConformityAssessments	Attribute
SupportingDocuments	ProcessDocumentation	Attribute
SupportingDocuments	TestReports	Attribute
SystemArchitecture	ArchitecturalComponents	Class

SystemArchitecture	ArchitectureOverview	Class
SystemArchitecture	ExternalSystemsIntegration	Class
SystemArchitecture	InteractionMechanisms	Class
SystemArchitecture	SAComputationalResources	Class
SystemContextMetricsAppropriateness	IntendedUseCasesAlignment	Class
SystemContextMetricsAppropriateness	SpecificUserGroupsOrEnvironmentsApplicability	Attribute
SystemContextMetricsAppropriateness	MetricsLimitations	Class
SystemDescription	GeneralFunctionality	Class
SystemDescription	ModelAndPerformanceCharacteristics	Class
SystemDescription	DeploymentScale	Class
SystemDevelopmentAppendices	AdditionalResources	Attribute
SystemDevelopmentAppendices	Glossary	Attribute
SystemDevelopmentAppendices	SupportingDiagramsAndDocumentation	Attribute
SystemPerformanceEvaluation	PerformanceMetrics	Class
SystemPerformanceEvaluation	ComplianceThresholds	Attribute
TechnicalDocumentation		Attribute
TechnicalMeasures	DeployersInterfaces	Attribute
TechnicalMeasures	MonitoringToolsAndAlerts	Attribute
Testing	LifecycleTesting	Attribute
Testing	Real-WorldTesting	Attribute
TestingProcedures	SamplingStrategies	Attribute
TestingProcedures	SimulatedConditions	Attribute
TestingProcedures	TestingProtocols	Attribute
TheDeclarationObject	ProductDetails	Attribute
ThresholdsAndBenchmarks	ThresholdsBasis	Attribute
ThresholdsAndBenchmarks	ThresholdDefinitions	Attribute
Tools	APIs	Attribute
Tools	Libraries	Attribute
Tools	SDKs	Attribute
Trade-Offs	EUAIActComplianceDesightTrade-Offs	Attribute
TrainingData	DataCharacteristics	Attribute
TrainingData	DatasetsUsed	Attribute
TrainingData	Provenance	Attribute
TrainingDatasheets	TrainingDataKnownLimitations	Attribute
TrainingDatasheets	SamplingTechniquesOrDataAugmentation	Attribute
TrainingDatasheets	TrainingMethodologiesAndTechniques	Attribute
TransparencyAndInformationProvision		Attribute
UpdateAndMaintenance	UpdateFrequency	Attribute
UpdateAndMaintenance	UpdateProcess	Attribute
UpdatedRiskAssessment	RevisedRiskEvaluation	Attribute
UseInstructions	DeploymentInstructions	Class
UserInterface	UserInterfaceDescription	Class
UserInterfaceDescription	Features	Attribute
UserInterfaceDescription	Overview	Class
ValidationAndTesting	MetricsAndResults	Class
ValidationAndTesting	ValidationAndTestingProcedures	Class

ValidationAndTestingProcedures	ProcedureDetails	Attribute
ValidationAndTestingProcedures	TestingDatasets	Attribute
VersionHistoryTable	Impact	Attribute
VersionHistoryTable	ReleaseDate	Attribute
VersionHistoryTable	ChangesSummary	Class
VersionHistoryTable	Version	Attribute
VulnerableGroupsConsideration	ImpactOnVulnerablePopulations	Attribute
VulnerableGroupsConsideration	SpecialMeasures	Attribute

Table 6: Detailed view of Application model classes and attributes

10.2 Resource model details

Table 7 presents in detail all classes and attributes of the Resource model. Due to the complexity of this model, references to (sub-)classes have been omitted in the table; they can be seen in the visual representation of the model in section 7.2.2. The classes that appear without any attributes in the table have only been used for semantic organisation of concepts.

Class Name	Attribute	Data Type
AttachedResource	mountPath	string
CPU	-	-
CPUConfig	cpuFrequencyCap	float
CPUConfig	frequencyScalingEnabled	boolean
CPUConfig	frequencyGovernor	string
CPUConfig	hyperthreadingEnabled	boolean
CPUConfig	firmwareOverrides	Map<string, string>
CPUConfig	microcodeVersion	string
CPUConfig	cpuIsolationPolicies	List<string>
CPUConfig	thermalThrottlingEnabled	boolean
CPUEnergy	-	-
CPUSocket	numOccupied	integer
CPUSocket	socketHealthStatus	string
CPUSocket	socketId	integer
CPUSocketConfig	socketEnabled	boolean
CPUSocketConfig	thermalOverride	boolean
CPUSocketSpec	socketType	string
CPUSocketSpec	supportedCpuFamilies	List<string>
CPUSocketSpec	maxPower	float
CPUspec	thermalDesignCurrent	float
CPUspec	virtualizationSupport	boolean
CPUspec	architecture	string
CPUspec	model	string
CPUspec	coreCount	integer
CPUspec	threadCount	integer
CPUspec	baseClock	float
CPUspec	maxClock	float
CPUspec	cache	float
CPUspec	instructionSet	string

CPUspec	flags	List<string>
Container	uid	string
Container	terminationReason	string
Container	startTime	string
Container	name	string
Container	statusState	string
Container	restartCount	integer
Container	imageId	string
ContainerConfig	cpuRequest	float
ContainerConfig	memoryRequest	float
ContainerConfig	cpuLimit	float
ContainerConfig	memoryLimit	float
ContainerConfig	volumeMounts	List<string>
ContainerSpec	args	List<string>
ContainerSpec	workingDir	string
ContainerSpec	livenessProbe	string
ContainerSpec	image	string
ContainerSpec	entrypoint	string
ContainerSpec	envVars	Map<string, string>
DPU	-	-
DPUConfig	offloadMode	string
DPUConfig	firmwareVersion	string
DPUConfig	virtualizationEnabled	boolean
DPUEnergy	-	-
DPUspec	coreCount	integer
DPUspec	cpuArch	string
DPUspec	sdkSupport	List<string>
DPUspec	arch	string
DeploymentDomain	provider	string
DeploymentDomain	costTier	string
DeploymentDomain	availabilityZone	string
DeploymentDomain	faultDomain	string
DeploymentDomain	zoneGroup	string
DeploymentDomain	topologyKey	string
DeploymentDomain	environment	string
DeploymentDomain	type	string
DeploymentDomain	region	string
DeploymentDomain	latencyTarget	float
DeploymentDomain	availabilityTarget	float
DeploymentDomain	description	string
Energy	-	-
EnergyConfig	powerCap	float
EnergySpec	tdp	float
EnergySpec	idlePower	float
EnergySpec	maxPower	float
ExecutionService	serviceVersion	string
ExecutionService	runtimeType	string

ExecutionService	schedulingPolicy	string
ExecutionService	name	string
ExecutionService	type	string
ExecutionService	endpoint	string
ExecutionServiceConfig	maxConcurrentJobs	integer
ExecutionServiceConfig	defaultTimeout	integer
ExecutionServiceConfig	retryPolicy	string
ExecutionServiceConfig	maxResourceUsage	Map<string, float>
ExecutionServiceSpec	execCapabilities	ExecCapability[]
ExecutionServiceSpec	supportedRuntimes	List<string>
ExecutionServiceSpec	isolationSupport	List<string>
ExecutionServiceSpec	orchestrationCompatibility	List<string>
FPGA	-	-
FPGAConfig	dynamicReconfiguration	boolean
FPGAConfig	configuredBitstream	string
FPGAConfig	virtualizationEnabled	boolean
FPGAEnergy	-	-
FPGASpec	logicCells	integer
FPGASpec	clockSpee	integer
FPGASpec	hdlLanguages	List<string>
FPGASpec	arch	string
GPU	-	-
GPUConfig	mpsEnabled	boolean
GPUConfig	virtualizationEnabled	boolean
GPUConfig	overclockEnabled	boolean
GPUEnergy	-	-
GPUSpec	computeCapability	string
GPUSpec	cores	integer
GPUSpec	hbmCapacity	integer
GPUSpec	hbmBandwidth	float
GPUSpec	arch	string
Location	country	string
Location	withinEU	boolean
Location	dataSovereigntyLevel	string
Location	latitude	float
Location	longitude	float
Location	address	string
Location	city	string
Location	postalCode	string
Location	jurisdictionType	string
MemoryComponent	type	string
MemoryComponent	capacity	integer
MemoryComponent	bandwidth	float
MemoryComponent	channels	integer
MemoryConfig	interleavingEnabled	boolean
MemoryConfig	overclockEnabled	boolean
MemoryConfig	errorCheckingEnabled	boolean

MemoryConfig	assignedClock	integer
MemoryProfile	memoryComponents	List<MemoryComponent>
MemorySpec	eccSupport	boolean
MemorySpec	maxClock	integer
MemorySpec	latency	float
Node	hostname	string
Node	labels	Map<string, string>
Node	taints	List<string>
Node	zone	string
Node	rack	string
Node	cpuSockets	List<CpuSocket>
Node	executionServices	List<ExecutionService>
Node	storageServices	List<StorageService>
Node	systemMemory	SystemMemory
Node	systemEnergy	SystemEnergy
NodeConfig	os	string
NodeConfig	kernelVersion	string
NodeConfig	tags	List<string>
NodeSpec	arch	string
NodeSpec	role	string
NodeSpec	physicalLocation	string
Pod	qosClass	string
Pod	nominatedNodeName	string
Pod	metadataName	string
Pod	metadataNamespace	string
Pod	metadataUid	string
Pod	statusPhase	string
Pod	statusStartTime	string
PodConfig	labels	Map<string, string>
PodConfig	nodeAffinity	string
PodConfig	resourceLimits	Map<string, float>
PodSpec	restartPolicy	string
PodSpec	replicas	integer
PodSpec	schedulingHints	List<string>
Processor	type	string
SharedMemory	memoryComponents	List<MemoryComponent>
SmartNIC	processors	List<Processor>
SmartNIC	osSupport	List<string>
SmartNIC	virtualizationSupport	List<string>
SmartNIC	targetUseCase	string
SmartNIC	hostCompatibility	List<string>
SmartNIC	priceTier	string
SmartNIC	osSupport	List<string>
SmartNIC	virtualizationSupport	List<string>
SmartNIC	targetUseCase	string
SmartNIC	hostCompatibility	List<string>
SmartNIC	priceTier	string

SmartNICConfig	networkOffloads	List<string>
SmartNICConfig	storageOffloads	List<string>
SmartNICEnergy	-	-
SmartNICSpec	pciInterface	string
SmartNICSpec	interfaceType	string
SmartNICSpec	vendor	string
SmartNICSpec	model	string
SmartNICSpec	memoryCapacity	integer
SmartNICSpec	storageCapacity	integer
SmartNICSpec	isProgrammable	boolean
StandaloneResource	tele	TelemetryInterface
StandaloneResource	conf	ConfigInterface
StandaloneResource	exec	ExecutionInterface
Storage	location	Location
Storage	storageType	string
Storage	capacity	integer
Storage	vendor	string
StorageConfig	provisionedSize	integer
StorageConfig	performanceTier	string
StorageConfig	encryptionEnabled	boolean
StorageFile	path	string
StorageFile	fileType	string
StorageFile	permissions	string
StorageObject	contentFormat	string
StorageObject	contentType	string
StorageObject	bucket	string
StorageService	availabilityZone	string
StorageService	throughput	float
StorageService	operationsRateLimit	integer
StorageServiceConfig	storageConfig	StorageConfig
StorageServiceConfig	mountLocations	StorageLocation[]
StorageServiceConfig	volumeSize	integer
StorageServiceConfig	mountOptions	List<string>
StorageServiceConfig	replicationEnabled	boolean
StorageServiceSpec	storageSpec	StorageSpec
StorageServiceSpec	storageBackend	Storage
StorageServiceSpec	supportedFileSystems	List<string>
StorageServiceSpec	maxVolumeSize	integer
StorageServiceSpec	accessProtocols	List<string>
StorageSpec	maxOperationsRate	integer
StorageSpec	avgLatency	float
StorageSpec	encryptionSupported	boolean
StorageSpec	raidLevel	string
StoredItem	id	string
StoredItem	name	string
StoredItem	size	long
StoredItem	owner	string

StoredItem	creationTime	string
StoredItem	lastModified	string
StoredItem	freshness	string
StoredItem	indexId	string
SystemEnergy	-	-
SystemEnergyConfig	maxNodePowerBudget	float
SystemEnergyConfig	powerCap	float
SystemEnergySpec	psuCount	integer
SystemEnergySpec	upsBacked	boolean
SystemEnergySpec	powerSupplyRedundancy	boolean
SystemEnergySpec	energyEfficiencyRating	string
SystemMemory	errorCorrectionMode	string
ThermalSpecProfile	fanSpeedPolicy	string
ThermalSpecProfile	thermalZone	string
ThermalSpecProfile	maxOperatingTemp	float
ThermalSpecProfile	throttleThreshold	float
ThermalSpecProfile	coolingType	string
ThermalSpecProfile	coolingPolicy	string

Table 7: Detailed view of Resource model classes and attributes

10.3 Telemetry model details

Table 8 presents in detail all classes and attributes of the Resource model. Due to the complexity of this model, references to (sub-)classes have been omitted in this table; they can be seen in the visual representation of the model in section 7.2.3. The classes that appear without any attributes in the table have only been used for semantic organisation of concepts.

Class Name	Attribute	Data Type
CPUtelemetry	throttlingPercent	Float
CPUUtilisationTelemetry	usagePercent	Float
CPUUtilisationTelemetry	idleTimePercent	Float
CPUUtilisationTelemetry	loadAverage	StatisticalValue
CognitiveDriftTelemetry	inputDistributionShift	Float
CognitiveDriftTelemetry	predictionShift	Float
CognitiveDriftTelemetry	modelVersionAtDrift	String
CognitiveDriftTelemetry	baselineReferenceId	String
CognitiveTelemetry	-	-
DeploymentStateTelemetry	deploymentId	String
DeploymentStateTelemetry	deploymentName	String
DeploymentStateTelemetry	targetNode	String
DeploymentStateTelemetry	status	String
DeploymentStateTelemetry	deploymentTime	DateTime
DeploymentStateTelemetry	workloadHash	String
DeploymentStateTelemetry	complianceTag	String
DeploymentStateTelemetry	deploymentRegion	String
DeploymentStateTelemetry	imageVerified	Boolean
DeploymentStateTelemetry	availableReplicas	Integer

DeviceTrustTelemetry	lastAttestationStatus	String
DeviceTrustTelemetry	patchLevel	String
DeviceTrustTelemetry	trustScore	Float
DeviceTrustTelemetry	uptime	Float
DriftTelemetry	driftDetected	Boolean
DriftTelemetry	detectedBy	String
DriftTelemetry	driftType	String
DriftTelemetry	driftScore	Float
DriftTelemetry	firstDetected	DateTime
DriftTelemetry	lastObserved	DateTime
DriftTelemetry	severityLevel	Integer
DriftTelemetry	driftConfirmed	Boolean
DriftTelemetry	driftRate	StatisticalValue
DriftTelemetry	driftCause	String
DriftTelemetry	affectedEntityId	String
EnergyTelemetry	currentPower	Float
EnergyTelemetry	averagePower	StatisticalValue
EnergyTelemetry	energyConsumed	StatisticalValue
EnvironmentTelemetry	humidityPercent	Float
EnvironmentTelemetry	vibrationLevel	Float
EnvironmentTelemetry	intrusionDetected	Boolean
LearningTelemetry	trainingTimeSec	Float
LearningTelemetry	epochCount	Integer
LearningTelemetry	convergenceMetric	Float
LocationTelemetry	latitude	Float
LocationTelemetry	longitude	Float
LocationTelemetry	isMobile	Boolean
MeasurementValue	value	Float
MeasurementValue	unit	String
MeasurementValue	method	String
MemoryPressureTelemetry	swapIn	StatisticalValue
MemoryPressureTelemetry	swapOut	StatisticalValue
MemoryPressureTelemetry	pageReclaims	StatisticalValue
MemoryPressureTelemetry	pageSteals	StatisticalValue
MemoryTelemetry	allocationFailures	StatisticalValue
MemoryTelemetry	pageFaults	StatisticalValue
MemoryTelemetry	TLBMisses	StatisticalValue
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	bandwidthUsagePercent	Float
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	sxThroughput	StatisticalValue
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	rxThroughput	StatisticalValue
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	usedCapacity	Float
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	freeCapacity	Float
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	activeCapacity	Float
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	inactiveCapacity	Float
MemoryUtilisationTelemetry	utilisationPercent	Float
ModelTelemetry	inferenceLatency	Float
ModelTelemetry	confidence	Float

NetworkTelemetry	averageLatency	Float`
NetworkTelemetry	packetLossPercent	Float
NetworkTelemetry	packetsSentRate	StatisticalValue
NetworkTelemetry	packetsReceivedRate	StatisticalValue
NetworkTelemetry	sxPacketsDroppedRate	StatisticalValue
NetworkTelemetry	rxPacketsDroppedRate	StatisticalValue
NetworkTelemetry	averageJitter	StatisticalValue
NetworkUtilisationTelemetry	bandwidthUsagePercent	Float
NetworkUtilisationTelemetry	sxThroughput	StatisticalValue
NetworkUtilisationTelemetry	rxThroughput	StatisticalValue
ObservationMetadata	precision	Integer
ObservationMetadata	confidence	Float
OrchestrationTelemetry	-	-
QueueMetric	queueLength	Integer
QueueMetric	avgWaitTime	StatisticalValue
SchedulerTelemetry	failedSchedulingAttempts	Integer
SecurityAndTrustTelemetry	trustDimension	String
StatisticalValue	minValue	Float
StatisticalValue	maxValue	Float
StatisticalValue	averageValue	Float
StatisticalValue	unit	String
StatisticalValue	method	String
StorageTelemetry	readOperations	StatisticalValue
StorageTelemetry	writeOperations	StatisticalValue
StorageTelemetry	readThroughput	Float
StorageTelemetry	writeThroughput	Float
StorageTelemetry	readLatency	Float
StorageTelemetry	writelatency	Float
StorageTelemetry	queueDepth	Integer
StorageTelemetry	readFailureRate	StatisticalValue
StorageTelemetry	writeFailureRate	StatisticalValue
StorageTelemetry	CRCErrrorRate	StatisticalValue
StorageUtilisationTelemetry	capacityUtilisationPercent	Float
StorageUtilisationTelemetry	readThroughput	StatisticalValue
StorageUtilisationTelemetry	writeThroughput	StatisticalValue
StorageUtilisationTelemetry	bandwidthUsagePercent	Float
TelemetryBase	timestamp	String
TelemetryBase	description	String
TelemetryBase	sourceId	String
TelemetryBase	sourceType	String
TemperatureTelemetry	temperature	Float
ThermalTelemetry	fanSpeed	Integer
ThermalTelemetry	thermalZone	String
TimeWindow	startTime	String
TimeWindow	endTime	String
TrustDriftTelemetry	trustScoreBefore	Float
TrustDriftTelemetry	trustScoreAfter	Float

TrustDriftTelemetry	previousTrustCategory	String
TrustDriftTelemetry	currentTrustCategory	String
TrustPolicyTelemetry	policyId	String
TrustPolicyTelemetry	policyScope	String
TrustPolicyTelemetry	policyType	String
TrustPolicyTelemetry	trustScore	Float
TrustPolicyTelemetry	policyThreshold	Float
TrustPolicyTelemetry	isCompliant	Boolean
TrustPolicyTelemetry	lastChecked	DateTime
TrustPolicyTelemetry	severityLevel	Integer
UserTrustTelemetry	loginSuccessFailureRate	StatisticalValue
UserTrustTelemetry	mfaUsageRate	StatisticalValue
UserTrustTelemetry	riskScore	Float
UtilisationTelemetry	-	-
WorkloadTelemetry	activeTasks	Integer
WorkloadTelemetry	taskRestartCount	Integer
WorkloadTelemetry	migrationLatency	Float
WorkloadTrustTelemetry	imageHashVerified	Boolean
WorkloadTrustTelemetry	runtimeIntegrity	String
WorkloadTrustTelemetry	trustScore	Float
WorkloadTrustTelemetry	originMetadata	String
WorkloadTrustTelemetry	isolationLevel	String

Table 8: Detailed view of Telemetry model classes and attributes